

1 California Tribal Advisors Share Contemporary Environmental Data and Information Needs

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22 **Abstract**

23 Long-term environmental changes and extreme events negatively affect the human and ecosystem health of
24 Indigenous and other rural communities. These disturbances include compounding and cascading hazards
25 across timescales, affecting those with limited resources to support environmental adaptation across the
26 hazard management cycle of planning, response, and recovery. Mitigating the varied negative effects of
27 hazards is critical for community resiliency; however, there is a limited understanding of the specific,
28 community-level information needed to support environmental adaptation and hazard management efforts.
29 Our objective is to identify how external researchers and personnel can collaborate with and provide
30 accessible, usable, and useful environmental information to Tribes for adaptation and hazard management,
31 according to Tribal perspectives. To build this understanding, ten semi-structured interviews were held with
32 Tribal environmental professionals in California. Interview questions included: What current or future
33 environmental conditions and hazards are you most concerned about? What information and resources do you
34 use and need to adapt to and manage these concerns? Using a thematic analysis approach to analyze the
35 exploratory interview data, seven identified themes highlight key needs pertaining to data sharing from public
36 agencies, communication between agencies and communities, and training materials to support protective
37 actions. Themes were distilled into seven recommendations intended for both agencies and Tribal (or other)
38 communities to improve environmental information access and use while honoring Tribal self-determination,
39 sovereignty, and worldviews. These recommendations can strengthen trust between groups to ensure
40 information is effectively communicated throughout the hazard management cycle and improve recovery and
41 resiliency following extreme events or long-term disturbance.

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45 **Introduction**

46 Indigenous communities' cultures, governance, economies, and holistic health are uniquely shaped by their
47 place-based ecocultural values and interconnections with natural environments [1-5]. Consequently, both
48 extreme weather events and long-term environmental change pose threats that vary according to each Tribe's
49 distinct geographic and cultural context. Across the United States, these threats fracture the foundational
50 interconnections that each sovereign Tribal political and cultural community maintains with its surrounding
51 ecosystems [1, 4, 6-12].

52 Yet, these same place-based interdependencies offer pathways for increasing resilience. Tribal governments
53 and intertribal organizations are actively developing and implementing environmental adaptation and hazard
54 management grounded in Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) [1, 10, 13-15]. Central to
55 these efforts is the stewardship of ecocultural species—plant and animal species that hold cultural
56 significance due to their roles in kinship, food, medicine, ceremony, and as indicators of environmental
57 health—reflecting interdependent relations between Indigenous communities and their natural environments
58 [4, 16].

59 California juxtaposes fire-adapted and fire-dependent landscapes with a highly variable Mediterranean
60 climate (i.e., alternating between pluvials and drought [17]) and ancient human-environment relationships [4,
61 16]. California's varied hydroclimate, extreme weather, and geography (from ecosystems to topography to
62 contemporary management and policy) combined with ongoing environmental change poses immediate and
63 gradual impacts to communities at local, regional, and state levels (Fig 1). Since time immemorial, California
64 Tribes have adapted to evolving environmental conditions and hazards to ensure social and ecological
65 resilience [4]. Today, Indigenous Peoples and partners actively work to revitalize ecocultural relationships
66 and resilience through Indigenous-led, guided, codeveloped, comanaged, or co-stewarded initiatives [4, 10].
67 Examples include the Indigenous Peoples Burning Network [18], which revitalizes the implementation of
68 cultural burns through intertribal support and TEK, and groups such as the Tribal EcoRestoration Alliance
69 [19] and Cultural Fire Management Council [20], which foster the economic, ecological, and cultural renewal
70 through Indigenous-led land stewardship. Tribal hazard management approaches include the development of
71 volunteer and paid Tribal Fire Departments (e.g., Hoopa Fire Department, Pechanga Fire Department, Pala
72 Fire Department, and Yurok Fire Department, among others). Established to protect Tribal lands and provide
73 mutual aid [21], these departments draw on longstanding Traditional Fire Knowledge [22] to address
74 immediate health and safety concerns while fostering long-term social, cultural, and ecological resilience [4,
75 16].

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77 **Fig 1. Examples of environmental impacts across California (2013 - 2026) based on National Centers**
 78 **for Environmental Information (NCEI) Storm Events Database [23] and past research [24-53] (S1**
 79 **Appendix).** Selected environmental impacts result from long-term change (i.e., fire exclusion, increasing
 80 aridity) and extreme weather events. Many selected events were noted in Tribal Advisor interviews as
 81 particularly impactful to Tribal communities, with several events otherwise unreported in NCEI or other
 82 publications. The methodology to produce the map is described in the S1 Appendix.

83 Partnerships between Tribes, agencies, communities, and nongovernmental organizations have cultivated co-
 84 management approaches designed to meet shared land stewardship objectives [16, 54-57]. Although Tribal
 85 Nations, intertribal organizations, and their partners continue to progress in environmental adaptation and
 86 hazard management, Tribes continue to face gaps in and barriers to externally-provided environmental
 87 information and services, within and beyond California [1, 9, 58-61]. Overcoming these barriers is critical, as
 88 environmental data are fundamental not only for evaluating land management approaches, but also for
 89 ensuring Tribal communities receive real-time weather data for timely preparedness alerts.

90 Information gaps are compounded by resource constraints that limit Tribal Nations' ability to collect, access,
 91 integrate, use, and communicate environmental information [1, 58, 60, 61]. Externally-provided data and tools
 92 frequently fail to offer culturally relevant information at actionable scales [61], nor do they follow FAIR
 93 (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) Guiding Principles for data management and CARE
 94 (Collective Benefit, Authority to Control, Responsibility, and Ethics) Principles for Indigenous Data
 95 Governance [1, 8, 62-65]. These limitations mirror broader regional challenges: Indigenous communities in
 96 the Southwestern United States have emphasized unmet needs for local climate conditions and impact
 97 projections, protection of TEK, and funding and training for Tribal data collection and monitoring [1].

98 Similarly, Tribes in the coastal Pacific Northwest cite adaptation barriers including collaboration and
99 partnerships, technical support, education, and workforce capacity, especially during project implementation
100 and maintenance following initial funding support [58]. For example, to navigate these systemic constraints,
101 Tule River Indian Tribe practitioners shared that viable adaptation strategies must bridge disconnections
102 between people and their environment while leveraging local expertise and stewardship [60].

103 To illuminate the environmental information barriers and needs shaping Tribal adaptation and hazard
104 management in California, we interviewed Tribal environmental professionals about their firsthand
105 experiences accessing, using, and communicating environmental information. Their perspectives were
106 synthesized to clarify how external agencies and organizations can better support Tribal adaptation and hazard
107 management. Of particular focus is how these agencies can provide accessible, actionable environmental
108 information while upholding principles of Tribal sovereignty and self-determination. Our study addressed
109 three primary research questions:

- 110 1. What weather conditions, long-term environmental hazards, and resulting community outcomes do Tribal
111 environmental professionals in California actively address?
- 112 2. What environmental data resources do these professionals use to develop, implement, maintain, and
113 communicate adaptation and hazard management plans for their lands and communities?
- 114 3. What are the key unmet needs and primary barriers to accessing, using, and communicating
115 environmental information? How can this information be provided in ways that overcome these
116 challenges and better support Tribal needs?

117 Semi-structured interviews were co-developed and conducted through a partnership between researchers at
118 the Cooperative Institute for Research in the Atmosphere and the Tribal Climate Health Project (TCHP)
119 (hereafter “research team”). Implemented through the Pala Band of Mission Indians in 2016, the TCHP
120 supports Tribal climate information needs by developing curriculum, resource inventories, and tools,
121 templates, and training for Tribal serving professionals [66]. In 2024, the TCHP invited 10 environmental
122 professionals representing different California-based Tribes to join its Tribal Advisory Board (TAB). This
123 initiative was driven by TCHP’s prior work highlighting the challenges Tribal Nations face in accessing
124 comprehensive, locally-relevant data on long-term water supply and wildfire vulnerability. The TAB
125 convenes several times a year to discuss and identify environmental information needs, related community
126 exposures, and best practices in adaptation.

127 Findings herein are based on discussions with individual TCHP TAB members (hereafter “Advisors”), who
128 shared their experiences using environmental information to inform their Tribe’s adaptation and hazard
129 management processes. We acknowledge each Tribe possesses their own knowledge, data, and sovereign
130 processes and has a unique history, culture, governance structure, and relationship to the land. To that end, we
131 synthesized shared themes across the interviews, considering place-based interdependencies while preserving
132 anonymity and confidentiality. By equipping Tribal Nations with accessible and relevant information,
133 external partners can better align their support with Tribally-defined goals, priorities, and timelines for
134 adaptation and hazard management.

135 **Methods**

136 **Data collection**

137 The research team co-designed and co-facilitated individual semi-structured interviews with 10 Tribal
138 environmental professionals comprising the TCHP TAB. We used a needs assessment approach to explore
139 Advisors' use of and needs for environmental information and communication resources based on their
140 personal professional experiences [54, 67, 68].

141 Advisors participated in the TCHP TAB through group discussions and activities, where they evaluated
142 climate adaptation tools, identified data gaps, and shared best practices for Tribal planning and decision-
143 making. Advisors met approximately six times between August 2025 and February 2026 and received \$2,000
144 in total compensation. TCHP also provided Advisors with customized climate vulnerability data their Tribe
145 could use to initiate or update climate adaptation plans or vulnerability assessments. All Advisors were either
146 Tribal members or employed by federally recognized Tribes. Advisors were purposively sampled to cover a
147 range of Tribal leadership and staff roles within environmental adaptation and hazard management. The
148 current and/or former professional roles of participating Advisors included: elected Tribal Councilmember
149 ($n=1$), Tribal Chairperson ($n=2$), Tribal Planning Manager ($n=1$), Tribal Environmental Director ($n=2$), Tribal
150 Environmental Protection Department Project Manager ($n=1$), Tribal Environmental Protection Department
151 Cultural Monitor ($n=1$), consultant ($n=1$), Tribal coordinator ($n=1$), and non-profit founder ($n=1$).

152 Semi-structured interviews were conducted with all 10 of the Tribal Advisory Board members. The TCHP
153 invited all Advisors to participate via email and verbally during a TAB meeting in August 2024. The
154 participant population was predetermined by TAB membership rather than guided by thematic saturation
155 principles [69], utilizing a key informant interview approach to explore the range of experiences and
156 perspectives within this specific expert advisory body [70-73]. LM scheduled interviews with Advisors and
157 EMW and BJH sent study overview and informed consent documentation, which included a request from the
158 research team for further information on Tribal Institutional Review Board (IRB) or consultation protocols for
159 collaborative research engagement. All 10 Advisors participated following informed consent procedures and
160 none requested further Tribal IRB or consultation protocols. The TCHP represented the Advisors by acting as
161 the data records holder and establishing guidelines for data collection, management, and dissemination [59].

162 We co-produced the semi-structured interview protocol (S2 Appendix) by jointly determining high-priority
163 concepts of study and tailoring questions to capture concepts relevant to the TAB [60, 74, 75]. A semi-
164 structured interview approach allowed the flexibility to explore and probe into complex, context-specific
165 Advisor perspectives [76, 77]. We revised the interview protocol after piloting it with one Tribal
166 environmental professional [74].

167 The interview guide began with introductory questions about Advisors' job roles and the environment-related
168 exposures and outcomes relevant to their Tribe. Subsequent interview questions explored how Advisors
169 access and apply environmental information and communications and how these resources could be improved
170 by external agencies and organizations. We defined environmental information to include a range of variables
171 capturing environmental conditions (e.g., weather, climate, ecology) and their long-term change. We intended
172 to capture the external drivers and internal exposures affecting human-environment interdependencies (e.g.,
173 ecocultural, health, and economic implications) for Tribal lands and communities. Communication aspects
174 included within-Tribe communication and information sharing from responsible decision makers to Tribes,
175 including alerts, warnings, briefings, and other modalities such as conference calls and in-person discussions.

176 All study materials were approved by The Colorado State University Institutional Review Board (IRB)
177 (#5979). Interviews were facilitated and analyzed by three research team members (EMW, BJH, and LM). All
178 Advisors provided verbal consent to participate and to be audio recorded at the start of the interview session.
179 Interviews took place via Zoom between September 3 and October 8, 2024. Interview duration ranged from
180 35–61 minutes with a mean duration of 46 minutes.

181 **Data analysis**

182 Audio recordings were transcribed via Zoom and then de-identified and reviewed by the research team to
183 ensure accuracy. After reviewing recordings and transcripts, we created a brief interview summary for each
184 interview using a standardized template (S3 Appendix) to capture initial interpretations of discussion topics
185 [60, 78]. We emailed each interview summary to the respective Advisor for their voluntary review, feedback,
186 and approval. This member-checking process provided an opportunity for Advisors to confirm whether their
187 perspectives were accurately captured—thus mitigating potential researcher bias—and to identify any Tribally-
188 sensitive or significant information to be redacted from transcripts and subsequent data analysis [74, 79, 80].

189 Next, we qualitatively coded and analyzed the de-identified transcripts using MAXQDA 2024 software [81].
190 Using an iterative, abductive (inductive-deductive) approach, our broader research and interview questions
191 informed an initial deductive codebook. Two research team members reviewed transcripts and interview
192 summaries to generate inductive codes that emerged to capture nuances and unforeseen discussion topics [82-
193 88]. The final codebook was established through iterative coding, discussion, and refinement [87, 88]. This
194 involved conducting inter-coder reliability assessments to validate codebook consistency and establish a
195 shared interpretative frame between two coders [89]. First, two coders independently coded one transcript and
196 discussed coding discrepancies, focusing on codes where the Brennan-Prediger kappa statistic fell below the
197 “moderate” strength of intercoder agreement (0.41 - 0.60) [78, 90-93]. Through reflexive discussions, we
198 iteratively refined code definitions and application instructions in the codebook, merging or adding codes
199 where necessary. Each coder then independently coded a second transcript to verify shared interpretations and
200 code applications at the paragraph level until the kappa statistic fell within the “moderate” to “substantial”
201 (0.61 - 0.8) range of agreement [91], ultimately reaching 78% agreement with a Brennan-Prediger kappa
202 statistic of 0.76. Finally, each coder independently coded four transcripts each according to the final codebook
203 (S4 Appendix).

204 We used an abductive thematic analysis approach to identify, analyze, and report patterns (themes) across the
205 coded transcription data [83, 85, 87, 88]. The identified themes reflect a “pattern of shared meaning” [94] that
206 unites data that might otherwise appear disparate but explains a large portion of the dataset [85]. Identified
207 themes serve as the analytic output of this study. We recursively refined themes, including by incorporating
208 Advisors’ optional interview summary feedback. Further, we invited Advisors to provide voluntary, optional
209 feedback on the full manuscript draft to further ensure that Tribal interests, needs, and knowledge were
210 accurately reflected herein. This iterative, reflexive, and collaborative approach intended to meaningfully and
211 accurately capture Advisor responses to interview and broader research questions [59, 74, 75, 79], particularly
212 as all but one of the research team are not Tribal members.

213 **Inclusivity in global research**

214 We sought Advisor perspectives at various points in the research process beyond data collection with the
215 intention to mitigate bias in this work. However, as in all research, the personal backgrounds and experiences
216 of co-authors influence research methodologies used, data collection and analysis approaches, and how

217 findings were interpreted and presented [95]. Understanding the positionality of the co-authors of this paper is
218 integral to the interpretation of these findings [95, 96] and the Indigenous cultural practice of self-locating
219 [97, 98].

220 EMW is not a Tribal member. She was raised in the ancestral lands of the Seneca, Adena culture, Hopewell,
221 and Monongahela peoples, later joined by Delaware, Shawnee, Mingo, and Haudenosaunee refugees, and
222 currently lives in the ancestral land of the Cheyenne, Arapaho, Ute, and other Indigenous peoples. She does
223 not live in California and acknowledges that her limited direct connection to the study area may influence her
224 interpretations of interview responses. As a social scientist at Colorado State University, she has been situated
225 within a Western science framework, and she recognizes the assumptions and constraints that lens carries into
226 qualitative research with Indigenous communities. Rather than attempting to explain or speak for historical
227 and current Indigenous adaptation practices, this work centers the knowledge shared by Tribal environmental
228 professionals. EMW's intention is to surface and amplify systemic information gaps in order to guide external
229 agencies toward information-sharing practices that respect and support Tribal needs and sovereignty.

230 BJH was raised among and currently lives on the ancestral lands of the Patwin, Coast Miwok, Washoe, and
231 Northern Paiute peoples; he is not a Tribal member. This geographic and relational context shapes both his
232 commitment to and limitations within this research. His academic training (B.S. in Geography, M.S. in
233 Atmospheric Science, Ph.D. in Geography) and more than two decades of work in ecological restoration,
234 mountain hydrology, climate services, and natural hazard prediction have been situated largely within
235 Western scientific institutions and frameworks, which carry embedded assumptions about knowledge,
236 evidence, and authority that may not always align with Indigenous ways of knowing and community-defined
237 needs. Since 2022, he has engaged in prescribed burning in California, receiving training from both traditional
238 and ecocultural fire practitioners, an experience that has deepened his respect for knowledge systems whose
239 ecological sophistication often exceeds what Western science has yet to fully account for. He acknowledges
240 the potential for his training and institutional context to introduce bias into his research approaches and
241 interpretations, and it is his intent that his work benefits the communities whose knowledge and experience
242 inform it, through collaboration and genuine integration of their perspectives throughout the research process.

243 LM is a career environmental scientist and former Tribal Liaison for the Office of Environmental Health
244 Hazard Assessment. LM's work for over 30 years has centered on government-to-government consultation
245 and analyzing climate and health vulnerability data for California Tribal Nations. While not a Tribal member,
246 LM approaches this research with awareness of systemic power dynamics and prioritizes listening and
247 collaboration. LM's commitment to inclusion is also shaped by extensive work in digital accessibility. LM
248 strives to ensure the research accurately reflects Tribal perspectives and needs.

249 IC is White, first generation American whose parents immigrated from France. She holds a Masters of Public
250 Health in epidemiology, a PhD in cell and molecular biology, and works for the County of San Diego, Public
251 Health Services. She is honored to be part of the County's Tribal Community of Practice, and to support work
252 groups focused on population health, climate change, and health equity for historically marginalized and
253 vulnerable groups.

254 SCG has a PhD in cultural anthropology and a Master of Legal Studies in Indigenous People's Law. She is
255 descended from European immigrants to the United States. She has worked for the Pala Band of Mission
256 Indians, a federally-recognized Tribe in San Diego County, since 2005. SCG's dissertation focused on the
257 culture, identity, and politics of the people of Pala through the lens of Indian gaming. Before being employed
258 by Pala, she did extensive ethnographic research and volunteered at Pala's cultural center; when she began her

259 dissertation research, the Tribe offered her the position of assistant director of the cultural center. While
260 working at the center, SCG established Pala’s Tribal Historic Preservation Office. In 2010, SCG became the
261 director of the Pala Environmental Department (PED), while continuing to fill the role of Tribal Historic
262 Preservation Officer. In 2026, she became the executive director of PED, where she supervises and directs
263 Pala’s cultural and environmental protection work. SCG’s years of experience working for Pala has
264 positioned her to interact and learn from Tribal members all over California and the country. She situates all
265 of her work through the lens of Tribal sovereignty and indigenous knowledge, prioritizes Indigenous voices,
266 and has developed deep understanding of and experience with the power imbalances that continue to
267 influence policy in Indian Country.

268 BLS is an enrolled member of the Citizen Potawatomi Nation and a Senior Tribal Engagement Specialist for
269 the State of California. He works closely with California Tribes and Indigenous communities with a focus on
270 Indigenous climate research and adaptation planning.

271 Additional information regarding the ethical, cultural, and scientific considerations specific to inclusivity in
272 global research is included in the Supporting Information (S5 Checklist).

273 **Results**

274 We identified seven themes across the interviews which we organized to align with the broader research
275 questions.

276 **Environmental conditions and hazards of concern to the Tribal Advisory** 277 **Board**

278 **Theme 1. Environmental hazard concerns centered on wildfire and water nexus**

279 Advisors identified 11 environmental conditions of concern to their Tribe (Fig 2a). The most prevalent
280 included extreme heat ($n=10$), mean daily temperature ($n=8$), and wind ($n=6$), and precipitation-related
281 hazards included rainfall ($n=4$) and snow ($n=4$). Extreme cold ($n=4$) was also noted. Additionally, Advisors
282 identified 10 environmental hazards of concern (Fig 2b). Wildfire ($n=10$), water supply/quality ($n=8$), air
283 quality ($n=7$), flooding ($n=7$), and drought ($n=5$) were the most prevalent across interviews.

284

285 **Fig 2a-b. Prevalence of (a) weather condition codes and (b) environmental hazard codes expressed as**
 286 **the count of total Advisors (n=10) who mentioned each at least once.** The prevalence of codes shown in
 287 (a) and (b) reflects the sample of Advisors, noting that as the Tribal Advisory Board included only one coastal
 288 Tribe from California, concerns related to tsunamis, marine heatwaves, and sea level rise may be
 289 underrepresented.

290 All Advisors indicated that wildfires were a “main concern” (Advisor 10) or “biggest stressor” (Advisor 5).
 291 Advisors described the emergence of “hotter, hotter fires” (Advisor 10) and that the “...fire season has
 292 expanded longer” (Advisor 7). Other prevalent weather-related concerns were wildfire-related: extreme heat
 293 (n=10) and increasing mean daily temperatures (n=8) create receptive fuels conducive to wildfire ignition and
 294 spread, with wind (n=6) acting in concert with hot weather and low humidity (n=4) to promote extreme fire
 295 behavior and challenge suppression efforts. Advisors related wildfire risk to “...the extreme...dry climate, the
 296 winds...” (Advisor 2), and several Advisors (n=5) associated increasing drought conditions with wildfire risk.
 297 Additionally, eight Advisors related their wildfire risk to the growth of invasive or non-native plant species,
 298 and three Advisors connected their wildfire risk to the lack of permissible prescribed or cultural burns.
 299 Advisor 2 described the environments surrounding their Reservation as a highly flammable “tinderbox”
 300 created by “...overgrowth of areas due to the fact that we can’t do wildfire prevention through, I guess, burn
 301 tracks or controlled burns for fire breaks”.

302 Advisors traced the complete fire cycle, beginning with drought, escalating into wildfire driven by heat and
 303 wind, and culminating with postfire threats. Wildfire-related hazards included air quality concerns ($n=7$) and
 304 postfire water quality and flooding ($n=4$). Driven by postfire soil conditions after drought-enhanced high
 305 severity wildfire, Advisor 7 described how postfire^[P]rainfall triggered landslides that damaged homes: “This
 306 is something new to us...it was an event I had never seen”.

307 **Theme 2. Projected weather-related cascading effects**

308 Discussions highlighted the cascading effects of weather and environmental conditions, revealing
 309 interconnections with (i) local ecosystems, (ii) cultural and economic sustainability, (iii) holistic health (e.g.,
 310 physical, mental, and community well-being), and (iv) built infrastructure (Fig 3).

311
 312 **Fig 3. Code co-occurrence network across interviews ($n=10$) at the coded-segment level.** Links represent
 313 segments where two or more codes were co-coded to the same segment of the transcript. Code co-occurrence
 314 reveals the interconnections between eco-cultural, socioeconomic, behavioral, and ecosystem impact codes.
 315 Line weights increase in thickness proportional to code co-occurrence frequency.

316 Nine Advisors identified information gaps in the availability of information regarding ongoing and projected
 317 climate-driven ecosystem changes. Advisor 7 shared that shifting weather and climatological conditions are
 318 “definitely exacerbating the decline in keystone species. And when I say keystone, that’s because they’re
 319 crucial to...my place, our culture”. Ecosystem changes were associated with changes in traditional food supply
 320 ($n=4$), the sustainability and resilience of cultural practices ($n=6$), and economic activity ($n=1$) (Fig 3). For
 321 instance, keystone plant species needed for cultural practices, including jewelry making and basketry, were
 322 described by Advisor 9 as “...our art or sole source of income”.

323 Advisors shared a need for information on the intersection of environmental conditions, associated cultural
 324 resource availability, and holistic Tribal well-being. Advisor 9 described how the viability of keystone species
 325 has declined under changing environmental conditions and “...trickles down right to how it affects people
 326 and...their whole health. I want to know the whole health impacts”. Another Advisor stressed a related
 327 concern: whether their Tribe would “have the same cultural resources. Living in certain parts of the
 328 community might not be feasible in 20 years if the temperature keeps increasing” (Advisor 2). They went on
 329 to describe the need for localized 10-to-20-year climate projections at an annual resolution to assess future
 330 environmental conditions.

331 Advisors also linked changing environmental conditions to infrastructure disruption and damage caused by
 332 flooding, strong winds, and wildfires, with postfire environments exacerbating precipitation- and wind-related

333 impacts (e.g., landslides, air pollution from dust, aeolian- and water-driven erosion, and falling trees). For
334 instance, four Advisors discussed how roadway damage has disrupted broader supply chains (e.g., medication
335 and medical treatment access, food, other goods and services). One Advisor described how past wildfires had
336 cut off one major supply route and led to erosion, disrupting their supply chain for groceries and “traditional
337 sources of food...our food sovereignty is affected, too” (Advisor 9). Hazards imposing transportation
338 disruptions can also hinder access to evacuation routes, especially for remote Tribes. Advisor 10 described
339 how their lands “...have one road in and one road out...where we would be trapped” given an emergency such
340 as wildfire. Evacuations were particularly concerning for Tribal members with pre-existing health conditions
341 who were described as “...just not mobile [enough] to be able to get out quickly in an emergency” (Advisor
342 10).

343 Health vulnerabilities compounded with remote locations “poses a challenge” (Advisor 7) for Tribes in
344 helping at-risk populations. For example, two Advisors highlighted that utility disruptions impact “elders who
345 need their medication in a refrigerator” (Advisor 7) or how Tribal members may “use generators...if there's a
346 flood [or] a fire, they can't get fuel for the generators, and people are on oxygen” (Advisor 10). The remote
347 location of many Tribes relates to other infrastructure constraints mentioned during extreme weather events
348 and hazards, such as concerns related to the continuity of communications technology (i.e., Wifi or cellular
349 reception).

350 **Environmental adaptation and hazard management resource needs**

351 **Theme 3. Consolidated and accessible Tribal information**

352 Tribal leadership, other Tribes, Tribal liaisons, and Elders were among the most prevalent sources of
353 environmental information (Fig 4a). More specifically, Tribal leadership ($n=10$) and other Tribes ($n=8$) were
354 most commonly mentioned (Fig 4b). All Advisors described the use and value of documented and archived
355 observations of Tribal lands over time, including Tribal leadership’s documentation ($n=8$), especially of
356 Tribal Chairmen. Advisor 3 described how early in their career, “...a lot of my knowledge, and what I was
357 taught was by the Tribal Chairman and the Tribal Vice Chairman...for them it was important to understand
358 [the changes they saw] and to make that known because they're responsible for [the villages]”. They went on
359 to describe how the Chairman had “hand drawings, stuff like that, that showed where the lakes, the drainages
360 in that area were because there was a creek there that had changed...the mapping for the parcels that the
361 county had...didn't match up to the conditions...” (Advisor 3) and, using TEK, the Chairman able to
362 determine changes in the Tribe’s natural and built infrastructure.

363

364 **Fig 4a-b. Information and communication code prevalence across interviews.** The prevalence of codes
 365 pertaining to (a) communication and information exchange between their Tribe and a range of other
 366 agencies/organizations, and (b) narrowing in on inter- and intra-Tribal communication and information
 367 exchange to support environmental adaptation and hazard management.

368 Eight Advisors also described how they have worked with neighboring Tribes on adaptation projects and
 369 information exchange (Table 1). Generally, Advisors shared that Tribal leaders, Elders, and neighboring
 370 Tribes use shared adaptation and hazard management resources and information. This was especially true in
 371 emergency situations, underscoring the value of inter-Tribal knowledge and resource sharing. However,
 372 Advisors expressed a need for Tribal adaptation and hazard management documentation to be more
 373 consolidated ($n=2$) and accessible ($n=3$), such as by documenting past planning efforts. One Advisor
 374 referenced an experience wherein new staff set out to create a drought plan unknowing that one already
 375 existed. This illustrates how accessible Tribal documentation may benefit “new staff when they come
 376 on...that gets overlooked a lot, and we start to recreate the wheel. And that’s just time and effort” (Advisor 1).
 377 To supplement oral traditions passed through storytelling, Advisors shared opportunities for documenting and
 378 recording adaptation and hazard management plans and lessons learned (Table 1).

379 Advisors also described how resource ($n=2$) and funding ($n=3$) constraints have limited environmental
 380 monitoring and documentation efforts. Funding opportunities for initial planning activities (i.e., conducting
 381 vulnerability assessments, launching adaptation projects) were perceived as more readily accessible.
 382 However, Advisors emphasized that gaps remain in securing sustained funding to monitor conditions and
 383 track ecological impacts over time (Table 1). Relatedly, five Advisors expressed needs for training, templates,
 384 and guidance on documenting weather and environmental conditions, outcomes, and lessons learned,
 385 especially considering workforce constraints. Advisor 1 described how “...simply reminding people of these
 386 types of things is really helpful...We’re all busy, especially a lot of folks at Tribes wear multiple hats, work on
 387 many, many different projects” not limited to hazard and environmental planning. Thus, templates and
 388 guidance for tracking and monitoring project progress may help the training process.

389 **Theme 4. Respectful information exchange and knowledge sharing**

390 In addition to Tribal information sources, a range of federal agencies were frequently mentioned as informing
 391 or supporting Tribal environmental adaptation and hazard management efforts. These included, but were not
 392 limited to, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)/National Weather Service (NWS),
 393 BIA, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), and United States Forest Service (USFS) (Fig 5).

394
 395 **Fig 5. Prevalence of federal agency communication and information used for environmental adaptation**
 396 **and hazard management across interviews (percentage and count of Advisors).** Note that ‘Interagency
 397 Groups’ mentioned by Advisors included AirNow, Incident Management Teams, and the National
 398 Interagency Fire Center.

399 Eight Advisors identified NOAA/NWS as a weather-related information resource. Advisors often described
 400 the use of NOAA/NWS for “maps...and big picture type thing[s] like, if I need to do a meeting and say,
 401 ‘Okay, here’s what it looks like, and here’s how it’s changing’” (Advisor 4). Another Advisor described using
 402 NOAA/NWS for “very important alerts about it [impactful weather] coming” (Advisor 1), referencing
 403 shorter- and longer-range forecasts and alerts that enable Tribes to “jump into action” and “make sure that the
 404 community has information” (Advisor 1). Data from the BIA was also mentioned, with one Advisor
 405 describing how “the BIA know[s] as much as they can know about Tribes, and they have to do it for federal
 406 reporting purposes” (Advisor 6), giving the example of documenting Tribal transportation infrastructure data.

407 Four Advisors described current involvement in interagency, multijurisdictional hazard management
408 meetings. For instance, Advisor 4 described how their Tribal Emergency Response Committee, including:

409 *“...community members, our casino staff and department heads, our Tribal government staff and*
410 *department heads, and then it also includes our police department and our partners, federal*
411 *agencies, state agencies, county and local... several meetings to come up with...a lot of different*
412 *stressors that contributed to coming up with these priorities and these strategies, and then the*
413 *strategies that we came up with in the adaptation plan” (Advisor 4).*

414 Six Advisors expressed a need for improved inter-jurisdictional relationships, particularly through co-
415 management or Tribally-led stewardship of land. Advisor 7 described that building “strong government-to-
416 government relationships” towards co-management of land can help “get on the right path not just for [our]
417 Tribe, but for every Tribe throughout the nation”. Advisors linked this need to insufficient information-
418 sharing from neighboring jurisdictions regarding adjacent land management activities, especially fuels
419 conditions and treatments. Without regular communication and coordination, the impact of neighboring
420 jurisdictions’ actions (or inactions) on adjacent fire ignition likelihood and fire behavior remains unclear,
421 perpetuating uncertainty for Tribal risk assessments and adaptation planning.

422 More specifically, Advisor 2 expressed a need to track traditional vegetation loss and invasive species. They
423 explained that invasive plant species erode soil, are highly flammable, and thus “...create this really
424 dangerous [condition] waiting...all around our community...I don't know if, if that's being tracked in a
425 meaningful way”. Concurrently, several Advisors described that their Tribal land or Reservation(s) bordered
426 federal land, and federal agencies have not been able to initiate fuels reduction projects. Advisor 3 described
427 how their Tribe has “worked with [a particular federal agency] on some projects”, but that these projects have
428 “been minimally successful” as one nearby mountain has not burned in over 80 years, creating fuels that have
429 “continued to grow and accumulate in a dangerous fashion”. To address these concerns, several Advisors
430 described the need for Tribally-led prescribed and cultural burns, explaining how cultural burns and debris
431 clearing “would slow the fires down, and maybe we could prevent the [fire incident] and all the smoke and all
432 the damage that it had on...our community” (Advisor 5).

433 In fostering government-to-government relationships, Advisors expressed two needs: (i) respecting Tribal
434 sovereignty and land stewardship approaches, and (ii) establishing relationships with Government agencies,
435 landowners, and community-based organizations. Related to the first need, several Advisors acknowledged
436 the need for Tribes “to be given the same grace that Forest Service gives itself” (Advisor 7) when it comes to
437 prescribed burns and wildfire management. This Advisor went on to share their experience in working with
438 other jurisdictions:

439 *“I see a lot more cultural burns and more like, ‘Okay, let's have this stewardship with them. Let's,*
440 *you know, let the Tribes work and do their thing’...I feel like it's being effective right now. But it's still*
441 *small scale. I wish we could get to a little larger scale, bigger scale” (Advisor 7).*

442 Several Advisors ($n=4$) highlighted their experience fostering relationships with trusted sources within
443 external agencies and organizations, such as community leaders and Tribal liaisons. One Advisor described a
444 long-term USFS employee as “the person I call because we have a relationship. I trust her. She'll point me in
445 the right direction, and she's been to the Reservation. She knows the concerns that we have, and she will talk
446 to the people that are there...she's their institutional knowledge point...it's been helpful with having that
447 person” (Advisor 3). Advisor 3 also acknowledged that Federal agency personnel turnover can hinder long-

448 lasting Tribal-federal agency relationships. This was described as a barrier to maintaining meaningful
449 government-to-government relationships.

450 While the majority of Advisors called for government-to-government information exchange and co-
451 stewardship of land, this necessitates Tribal self-determination and sovereignty. Various funding agencies
452 often “require partnerships” (Advisor 9) that are not always desired “because then we [Tribes] have to give up
453 a piece of our sovereignty. And then we also are still looking through a Western American mainstream
454 cultural view...We need to uphold our sovereignty, and we need to fortify that sovereignty” (Advisor 9).
455 Advisor 9 described how Tribal approaches to maintaining and monitoring water resources, for example, may
456 be different from the approaches used by state and federal agencies.

457 **Theme 5. Training and templates for information sharing**

458 Nearly all Advisors ($n=9$) noted that Tribal leadership needs accessible, interpretable tools to communicate
459 environmental risks and protective actions with Tribal members. Advisors emphasized tailoring these
460 communications by (i) using visualizations (figures or photographs) ($n=6$), and (ii) provides Tribally-relevant
461 information (i.e., spatially explicit; storytelling) ($n=5$) while (iii) addressing audience-specific needs and risk
462 factors such as rural residency. Advisors explained that they would like “to know more specifically, what it is
463 that [the data from other agencies] is telling” (Advisor 9). Generally, Advisors expressed that training,
464 outreach material templates, and tailored protective action guidance could support Tribal leaders’
465 communication with Tribal members.

466 Some Advisors ($n=2$) explained their Tribe is capable of creating graphics and visuals related to historical and
467 projected environmental conditions. However, they expressed they would benefit from educational
468 opportunities to create more effective visualizations that help “to interpret the visual data” (Advisor 8). This
469 may include “a standardized template or a set of infographics or graphics that will always consistently depict
470 certain issues to be on alert for” (Advisor 2). This information could be shared via flyers, social media, and
471 other communication platforms.

472 Beyond graphical displays, four Advisors emphasized the power of sharing stories or photos to communicate
473 environmental conditions and risks. Advisor 1 explained that graphical outreach materials effectively support
474 Tribal member preparedness when framed “in a kind of a Tribal context”. They noted that because “Native
475 culture is very storytelling based...giving just kind of cold, hard facts and data isn’t really the way to do it”
476 (Advisor 1). Consequently, Advisors expressed a need to communicate environmental information to Tribal
477 members “in a little bit more of a story format” (Advisor 1) connected to community impacts. Culturally
478 contextualized communication relates to Theme 02 (the need for information on cascading effects),
479 supporting Tribal leaders in delivering weather and hazard warnings and protective action guidance to Tribal
480 members by additionally integrating the articulation of Tribal values and constraints into this guidance.
481 Finally, most Advisors ($n=7$) highlighted the need to tailor environmental communications to an audience’s
482 educational levels, learning styles, values, and exposure to hazards. Advisors described how supplemental
483 resources and training opportunities focused on Tribal leaderships’ science communication may enhance how
484 they communicate environmental information with Tribal members.

485 **Towards more accessible and actionable environmental information**

486 **Theme 6. Information at actionable scales**

487 Nearly all Advisors ($n=9$) described a need for more accessible, localized environmental information (both
488 historical and projected) that is more readily integrated into hazard management and adaptation efforts.
489 Advisors described how “I’m looking for specifics, and I have a hard time finding them...I’m trying to find the

490 real data. And it's just really hard" (Advisor 4). Historical, localized wildfire, sea level rise, and temperature
491 data were described as particularly challenging to access. Geographic resolution was an expressed gap ($n=7$)
492 for both historical and projected environmental data, with several Advisors speaking to state-level climate
493 assessments that are "not local, that's all of California" (Advisor 4) and therefore less locally relevant and
494 thus actionable.

495 While historical information remains difficult to access, Advisors noted that mapping efforts from other
496 agencies were informative. For instance, Advisor 3 described how:

497 *"We started working with the [federal agency] and looking at different types of grant opportunities, and*
498 *getting...some of the historical information that was available, and some of the mapping that they*
499 *do...that makes it actually easier to do my job. Finding that stuff online was very helpful. But like I said*
500 *that the day-to-day stuff is a lot of that is phone calls, emails, texting, or using the radio" (Advisor 3).*

501 Advisors shared that higher spatial resolution information could improve data interpretation and enable "the
502 ability to share that, and having maybe outreach materials prepared" (Advisor 1), connecting to Theme 05
503 (training and templates for information sharing). Effective examples of higher resolution information were
504 described, such as Advisor 1's use of U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service's climate impact models that localized
505 "potential effects to different areas where threatened or endangered species exist...And they were trying to
506 look at the effects of climate change on this endangered plant, and if it's only in this area and we're
507 experiencing severe climate changes, is that plant gonna be able to continue to survive?" (Advisor 1). This
508 example demonstrates that applying localized weather and climate data helps reveal cascading environmental
509 consequences (Theme 02) in a way that specifically addresses Tribal needs and values (Theme 05).

510 **Theme 7. Timely, localized hazard alerts**

511 Five Advisors expressed the need for other agencies to disseminate more timely and localized weather and
512 hazard alerts to Tribal leadership, especially for wildfire, smoke, and flood warnings. Advisors who expressed
513 this need tended to note the geographic dispersion of their Tribe, one explaining that "professionally, I need to
514 be aware of what's happening" (Advisor 8) within and near their Tribe's multiple reservations that are
515 approximately an hour apart. Geographical dispersion of Tribal members can make disseminating alerts
516 challenging. Covering a broad region increases the workload of already busy personnel, who monitor and
517 alert Tribal members and their relatives of rapidly evolving hazards like wildfires. To mediate this workload,
518 Advisors described that it "would be nice if somebody would call you up, but I just I don't think that's gonna
519 happen...I am sending out information on a wildfire that's happening...wherever because they have relatives
520 there. And so they need to know if those relatives are being evacuated or are in harm's way" (Advisor 4).

521 Advisor 4 also expressed the desire for more locally specific updates, hoping for somebody to "just call me
522 and say, 'Hey, weather just changed'..." in reference to extreme precipitation events.

523 Several Advisors noted technology constraints that hinder communication and therefore situational awareness
524 between Tribal leadership and Tribal members. These include cell phone service, access to TV/Wifi, and
525 electricity and these constraints also create difficulties in communication between utilities companies and
526 Tribal leadership. One example mentioned that applies to many locations in California and beyond included
527 inconsistent warnings from utilities regarding the potential for de-energization events (i.e., Public Safety
528 Power Shutoffs) ahead of critical fire weather.

529 In addition to localized and imminent threats (e.g., wildfire, extreme heat, and flood risks), Advisors
530 discussed opportunities for tracking and communicating longer-term regional air quality conditions. While
531 multiple Advisors shared that their Tribe monitors air quality, some Advisors expressed concern that this
532 information "either [isn't] communicated quickly enough or maybe not in as meaningful a way that it gets out

533 to the people” (Advisor 2). To better anticipate and communicate regional reductions in air quality, Advisor 2
534 proposed an idea for other agencies to “email...our environmental department” information and warnings
535 related to wildfire suppression progress and associated smoke transport. This type of information could then
536 be posted to social media for broader dissemination (Table 1).

537 **Table 1. Selected Interview Quotes Representing Each of the Seven Interview Themes.**

Theme	Representative Quotes
1. Environmental hazard concerns centered on wildfire and water nexus	<p>“...over the last 10 years...the droughts we’ve had...have not had enough water on the Reservation...lack of water and the wildfire risk is really high” (Advisor 7).</p> <p>“In the winter, when we have flash floods, we're also facing issues with flash [floods] due to, you know, the erosion and the damage that the [specific fire incident] had started. More drier weather” (Advisor 5).</p>
2. Projected weather-related cascading effects	<p>“...worry is [the] decrease in our species range. As a Tribe, we have significant cultural connections to certain animals and plants that are native to our area” (Advisor 8).</p> <p>“...we only have one highway...and those are our major supply chain routes, and then we have all these rivers and creeks with bridges...Those routes are blocked...what do we do? We have to be able to plan for that” (Advisor 9).</p>
3. Consolidated and accessible Tribal information	<p>Tribe described as “unique in many situations where we've encountered issues of emergency within the valley. The valley kind of bands together, because we are so rural and isolated that we know that we have to depend on only ourselves” (Advisor 2).</p> <p>"Oral traditions are passed down through storytelling...And so I think people tend not to document and record things as much as possible” which sets up a need for “a little bit of guidance and assistance in helping people kind of think about the type of data that they need to record, and those After Action Reports and...Are you documenting all of your disasters? Are you documenting all of your fixes?” (Advisor 1).</p> <p>“...the money to do the projects is easier to get than the money to maintain what you've done. And so you know, a lot of it's in-house as far as keeping track of what the impacts [are], good and bad” (Advisor 3).</p>
4. Respectful information exchange and knowledge sharing	<p>“...look at increasing the type of management we're doing, not just, you know, going out and lighting fire, but doing some other things as well...potentially raking areas, spacing out like the the underbrush growth, like the [prescribed] fires need to be bigger” (Advisor 6).</p> <p>“It's the land that's not being managed. It's management of those lands, and we want to have an agreement or to work with the government and say, ‘Hey, give us a let's get a portion of that land. Let's give us a chance to manage it, say, I don't know, small scale. Let's start 10 to 100 acres or a hundred to 250 acres. Give us this portion of land. Let us manage it, and let's see. Let's put fire on it. Let's treat the land. How our ancestors did for hundreds of years, and I see that coming back” (Advisor 7).</p> <p>“[Tribes] are gonna look at it differently than a State or Federal agency is going to. And that means we're gonna monitor it differently. We're gonna see the connections different” (Advisor 9).</p>
	<p>Preference for presenting environmental information “in a little bit more of a story format and kind of, you know, explain why...this is important to people, then that’s very beneficial” (Advisor 1).</p>

5. Training and templates for information sharing	Need for training/tutorials "...to build our own templates that work for our posters or our flyers, or our Facebook posts. That would be useful, and you know, we can communicate things within hours. We're a very small community...I would say that there doesn't have to be such a high out lead time on something for our citizens and our everyday people" (Advisor 2).
6. Information at actionable scales	<p data-bbox="392 272 1997 337">"How often are the fires happening? How big are the fires? Where are they happening at? That was just going through and researching old newspaper articles...It's just not easy" (Advisor 4).</p> <p data-bbox="392 370 1997 435">"The first thing that pops in my mind...coarse versus finer grain data. It was very challenging to get, you know, projected effects for our local area" (Advisor 1).</p>
7. Timely, localized hazard alerts	<p data-bbox="392 467 1997 532">"...emergency information, for like flash flood warning, or, you know, be on the lookout for high winds in this area...even air quality into that type of a system. I think that would be a really fantastic way to communicate that type of information to the community at large".</p> <p data-bbox="392 565 1997 662">"...if [a fire is] under control by 50% in the next two days we would anticipate that you need to prepare for air quality risk due to smoke particles...I think truly an incredible thing for the community...just kind of like CAL FIRE does where they give a constant update of what fires in California are like. Or if it was even a text, alert system" (Advisor 2).</p>

538

539 **Discussion**

540 Tribal adaptation strategies are uniquely derived from TEK and place-based interdependencies [1, 4, 13].
541 Historically and today, Tribes both within and beyond California adapt traditional practices in response to
542 shifting environmental extremes and hazards to achieve long-term ecocultural objectives and socio-ecological
543 resilience [4, 6, 59, 99]. For millennia, Tribes have sustained distinct knowledge systems to observe, monitor,
544 record, and communicate environmental information and maintained ways of anticipating and adjusting to
545 environmental change [4, 6, 15].

546 The perspectives of interviewed TCHP Tribal Advisors' echoed the relational ethics system framework,
547 where environmental health is inseparable from human health, culture, and the viability of ecocultural species
548 essential for kinship, food, and medicine [1-3, 8, 15, 60, 97, 100-105]. Indigenous relational worldviews
549 tether people and their environments through respectful relationships and a duty to care for and continuously
550 rejuvenate the land [15]. This relationship is entirely reciprocal; the decline of a keystone species is not only
551 an ecological shift, but a cascading threat to Tribal well-being [15, 105].

552 Across Advisor discussions, the most prevalent sources of environmental information were Tribal leadership
553 and Elders, other Tribes, and Tribal liaisons, demonstrating the critical role of information sharing within and
554 between Tribes to document and interpret environmental change demonstrates how Indigenous communities
555 have developed "tools to support localized adaptation planning and action independently" [1, 4]. The reliance
556 on resources provided by Tribal governments underscores the value of place-based, relational knowledge
557 systems used in Tribal environmental adaptation and hazard management [61].

558 Accelerating environmental shifts may diverge from historical baselines and long-standing ancestral
559 observations [106]. Compounded by historical displacement and land-use change, these unprecedented
560 conditions create needs for external information to complement Tribal knowledge of complex weather and
561 environmental relationships [16, 21, 54]. Our results underscore the multifaceted and systemic barriers
562 California Tribal environmental professionals face when accessing, using, and communicating information for
563 adaptation and hazard management. While external agencies produce vast amounts of environmental data, a
564 persistent disconnect remains between what they produce and the contextualized needs of Tribes [61].
565 Advisors identified external sources of environmental information used to inform hazard management, shape
566 adaptation plans, and understand environmental stressors. Yet, they consistently reported that a lack of
567 accessible, localized, and temporally relevant weather and climate data limits the utility of those resources.

568 In particular, current findings highlight the centrality of wildfire and cascading environmental impacts in
569 Tribal adaptation planning [1, 58, 100]. Compounded by fire exclusion, long-term drought, extreme heat, and
570 wind, all 10 Advisors highlighted the centrality of wildfire and cascading environmental impacts in Tribal
571 adaptation planning. This sequence is a common occurrence culminating in large, high severity wildfires
572 across California (Fig 1). Continuing this sequence, Advisors described how intensifying and longer fire and
573 drought seasons were connected to cascading air quality, water quality, and postfire flooding and debris flow
574 concerns (Fig 1). Related state-level or regional climate assessments were often seen as too coarse to inform
575 local decision-making, echoing critiques regarding the scale and Tribal relevance of available information [8,
576 61]. State-level or regionalized datasets and models frequently lack the resolution and overlook the
577 complexities inherent in dynamic landscapes with varied and interrelated hazards and impacts [106], with
578 examples including drought-induced wildfire that degrades Tribal water and ecocultural resources.

579 Furthermore, environmental data presented as static, isolated parameters often falls short of capturing the
580 many dimensions of climate or environmental vulnerability and the human role in tending to the land [106].

581 Advisors' relational worldviews revealed a critical need for integrated, systems-based thinking and
582 information that connects environmental conditions with the viability and sustainability of ecocultural
583 resources over multiple generations [1, 4, 101, 102]. Supporting this perspective, Chief et al. [74] argue that
584 scientific frameworks must account for the broader place-based interdependencies between social, cultural,
585 and governance dimensions inherent to Indigenous knowledge systems, rather than treating ecological entities
586 strictly as quantifiable metrics or economic resources. As such, there remains unmet needs for vulnerability
587 assessments and subassessments that embrace dynamic and relational ethics systems [104, 106, 107].

588 Beyond information needs related to relational systems, Advisors expressed gaps in inter-jurisdictional
589 information exchange. Specifically, they noted neighboring jurisdictions often fail to share information
590 regarding vegetation composition, fuel loads, and management actions such as fuel treatments. This lack of
591 cross-boundary data integration introduces significant technical uncertainty into Tribal vulnerability
592 assessments and limits long-term Tribal adaptation planning and implementation [4, 22, 100].

593 Although Indigenous peoples increasingly collaborate with academic, governmental, and nongovernmental
594 scientists to utilize localized, downscaled environmental information and tools [6], persistent structural
595 barriers remain. Misalignments between conventional Western and Tribal resource management frameworks
596 limit Tribal environmental adaptation [4, 22, 57, 100, 108, 109]. These systemic challenges are apparent in
597 cross-boundary land management, where restrictive agency consultation processes [109] and regulatory
598 barriers to prescribed and cultural burns reduce ecosystem resilience while accelerating regional wildfire risk
599 [4, 100].

600 These overarching structural limitations directly impact Tribal adaptation, creating a pronounced need for
601 information consolidation and communication within Tribes. Advisors explained how complementary
602 guidance, training, and/or templates co-developed between Tribes and external agencies can bolster existing
603 internal information flows and enhance documentation and knowledge transfer within and between Tribes
604 [61]. Advisors noted how training and guidance for documenting weather and environmental conditions,
605 outcomes, and lessons learned over time can complement knowledge passed through storytelling and other
606 ways of communication. This could also support many Tribal staff who “wear multiple hats” (Advisor 1) and
607 manage numerous projects simultaneously. These barriers mirror those in the Pacific Northwest. There,
608 Tribes similarly called for localized environmental data and associated technical assistance, specialized
609 technical services to support Tribes' adaptation planning and implementation, and opportunities (funding,
610 training) to build internal capacity and preserve institutional knowledge and capacity to address long-term
611 adaptation needs [58]. Regional parallels also extend to communication needs, with PNW Tribes emphasizing
612 the necessity of tailored outreach mechanisms, inter-Tribal information sharing networks, and educational
613 products to establish a common guidance, reduce misinterpretation, and cultivate partner support [58].

614 To address these systemic data sharing, planning capacity, and communication misalignments and limited
615 internal capacity, Advisors articulated a need for co-management agreements that enable Tribal self-
616 determination—specifically regarding leading prescribed cultural burns and traditional stewardship practices.
617 Literature distinguishes “co-management” from weaker “co-stewardship” models, where co-management
618 agreements recognize Tribal sovereignty and decision-making authority through participatory frameworks in
619 early stages of project identification, planning, and implementation [56, 100]. Advisors described that while
620 establishing rights and assured access to ancestral lands remains a barrier to expanding ecosystem restoration,
621 leveraging co-management can provide interim opportunities to build Tribal trust, capacity, and equitable
622 environmental decision-making [9, 56, 110].

623 Despite the potential of co-management, some Advisors expressed concern about the protection of Tribal
624 sovereignty, self-determination, and the potential imposition of Western frameworks within collaborative
625 agreements [56, 100, 108]. Perspectives on what inter-jurisdictional co-management and collaboration should
626 look like varied across Advisors. This underscores the need for adaptive, tailored approaches that uphold
627 Tribal self-determination and sovereignty [108, 111]. Building long-term, trust-based relationships is essential
628 and must be grounded in a moral responsibility to respect Indigenous knowledge systems as encompassing
629 social, cultural, and political dimensions beyond mere data [57, 74, 108] while honoring CARE Principles
630 (Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics) for Indigenous Data Governance [63,
631 112, 113] and FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) for scientific data management
632 [63, 65]. This includes honoring lived knowledge—knowledge and expertise embodied through experience—
633 and embracing an Indigenous relational worldview through respectful, reciprocal relationships connecting
634 people and the environment [97, 100, 103].

635 **Recommendations**

636 Based on the insights and gaps identified by Advisors, we offer actionable pathways for external
637 environmental information providers to better support Tribally-defined needs for environmental adaptation
638 and hazard management efforts. Synthesizing the thematic analysis with existing literature and the research
639 team’s applied expertise yielded seven overarching recommendations structured around the phases of
640 environmental adaptation and hazard management (Table 2). These recommendations center Tribal
641 environmental information needs, honor data sovereignty and self-determination, and embrace reciprocal,
642 relational worldviews [1, 61, 64, 74, 97, 100, 103, 108]. The following text details each recommendation
643 alongside supporting interview findings and existing literature.

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651 **Table 2. Recommendations and Potential Actions to Enhance Tribal Environmental Information**
 652 **Access and Use across the Hazard Management Cycle.**

Phase	Recommendations	Potential Actions
Planning and Preparation	1. Consider Tribal needs over the full, long-term life cycle of environmental adaptation. Allocate resources accordingly.	(a) Applicants could inquire with colleagues (internal and external) and document previously realized unanticipated costs and account for these in future projects. (b) Funding agencies can encourage applicants to consider full project lifecycle needs in their proposals and budget resources accordingly.
	2. Share accessible, usable information with Tribal leadership, especially as related to federal, state, and local land management activities.	(a) Coproduce and follow best practices for data sharing. (b) Foster relationships between data and model output producers and users that enable co-generation of information. Producers will benefit from listening to and iteratively implementing user needs. Producers should communicate technical limitations and empower users to ask how to best apply products to meet needs. Make dedicated climate services available to Tribes.
	3. Honor and include TEK, Tribal stewardship, and cultural practices in government-to-government relationships and agreements.	(a) Inquire with Tribes in the initial, conceptual phase of project planning to establish preferred processes for consultation and subsequent collaboration. (b) Develop and formalize co-management agreements that respect Tribal data sovereignty and integrate TEK to collectively shape objectives and implement work.
	4. Deepen local understanding of how past and future environmental changes compound and cascade to impact Tribal lands and health.	(a) Establish working groups composed of involved partners (see 3b) to develop initial understandings of causes and effects, then include the public via a participatory process to refine. (b) Document events of interest/impact as they occur and incorporate immediate and cascading effects. Update information as outcomes are further identified and understood.
Response	5. Assess how weather warning systems reach Tribes, especially those with dispersed remote populations.	(a) Create, distribute, and maintain a repository of existing alert and communication systems to which Tribes could subscribe. (b) Gather structured feedback from Tribes during outreach events and incident briefings regarding alert timeliness and accessibility. Document system failures and areas for improvement directly into the repository.

Recovery	6. Co-produce training and guidance material for Tribal leaders to document environmental extremes, risks, and outcomes.	(a) Ensure iterative feedback is sought from Tribal leadership and the broader community (see 5a-b). (b) Incorporate information from 2a-b, 4b, 5b, 7b and apply techniques used to perform “Lessons Learned” or following the style of “After Action Reviews”. Plan ahead of time for recovery, envisioning the initiation point and defining what short- and long-term recovery may look like to produce guidance.
Planning, Response, Recovery	7. Co-produce training and outreach materials with Tribal leaders to help them easily share environmental information within their communities.	(a) Working groups, individual agencies, and Tribes can co-produce training materials; consider budgeting resources (1a) to support these efforts. (b) Incorporate events of interest (4b) into training materials as case studies or storylines, especially if “Lessons Learned” (6a-b) are available. (c) Consider creating templates that follow best practices to ensure Tribal relevance while remaining adaptable to broader communities.

653

654 **1. Consider Tribal needs over the full, long-term life cycle of environmental**
655 **adaptation. Allocate resources accordingly.**

656 During planning and preparation, ensure funding and other in-kind support are made available by funding
657 agencies and written into grant proposals and other funding mechanisms by applicants to cover the life cycle
658 of Tribal adaptation efforts, including training, data collection, analysis, storage, and maintenance. This can
659 include planning and implementation as well as the longer-term maintenance, monitoring, data storage or
660 hosting, and training opportunities to ensure continuity of projects as staffing changes [61]. Financial
661 resources that enable Tribes to self-determine and implement adaptation efforts from planning through
662 monitoring (and in some cases, recovery and/or restoration) will support necessary “action on the ground”
663 [54]. This may include installation, maintenance, data storage, and online hosting of their own monitoring
664 systems for local environmental variables, including cameras, meteorological observations, air quality, soil
665 moisture, and streamflow. The costs and timelines for re-treatment of fuels reduction or invasive species
666 removal should be considered by both funding agencies and applicants, as multiple cycles of treatment may
667 be necessary to ensure the management goals and objectives are achieved. Documenting training needs and
668 lessons learned throughout will help pass on knowledge to new staff; training may also include conference
669 attendance to learn best practices, receive feedback on upcoming projects, and expand professional networks.
670 Additionally, allocating resources to report project milestones and benefits back to the community can help
671 maintain support and increase engagement for adaptation activities [114].
672 Entities that fund adaptation efforts can consider how their programs can more flexibly respond to unforeseen
673 circumstances (e.g., wildfire, storm damage, invasive insect outbreaks) [100]. They can also review and
674 include proposal scoring metrics that encourage full project life cycle consideration and broader impacts. This
675 can provide Tribes more autonomy and flexibility in making allocation decisions and enhance community
676 support [8, 58].

677 **2. Share accessible, usable information with Tribal leadership, especially as**
678 **related to federal, state, and local land management activities.**

679 Local, state, and federal jurisdictions, as well as private landowners neighboring Tribal lands, can support
680 Tribal situational awareness, risk assessments, and adaptation activities by documenting and sharing
681 information on land management activities and environmental conditions with Tribal governments. To
682 maximize accessibility and utility, we recommend that this information (for example, fuels treatments, fire
683 history, soil erodibility, and infrastructure) is consolidated (see Theme 02), shared using common formats for
684 geospatial data (e.g., .csv, .netCDF, or shapefiles), and hosted in data repositories or warehouses (e.g., the
685 Treatment and Wildfire Interagency Geodatabase (TWIG) [115] or the WIFIRE Data Commons [116]).
686 Preferably, this information will also be made available via downloadable maps (see Theme 04) following
687 standard cartographic best practices and geospatial data protocols that include metadata and complementary
688 documentation to enable use when geographic information system capabilities are limited. In all cases,
689 sensitive Tribal data must be protected following Tribal guidance.

690 Further, we recommend providing technical assistance to Tribes and other users of the data through
691 comprehensive metadata, how-to (or wiki) pages, and upon-need support provided by dedicated climate
692 services. Opportunities exist for experts in other jurisdictions to provide technical expertise (i.e., training and
693 tutorials) and long-term capacity-building resources (i.e., financial resources) to support the application of
694 environmental information in continuous, Tribal-led adaptation efforts [58, 61]. Additionally, data
695 management practices can align with frameworks such as those outlined by the Urban Indian Health Institute,
696 which advocate for weighing community protective and cultural factors against disparities, refining research
697 methodologies for small populations, and centering community-held knowledge to guide data investments
698 [117]. We believe an additional opportunity exists in the establishment of monitoring networks: partnerships
699 between agencies and Tribes could facilitate sustainable funding for long-term data collection.

700 Collaboratively siting stations to meet multiple needs and ensuring online data availability can support varied
701 agencies, partners, and communities, both locally and beyond, through information regarding wildland fire
702 danger, drought conditions, infrastructure, water resources, and weather conditions. This last researcher-
703 inferred statement will require agreements to be reached between Tribes and other agencies or entities
704 regarding data management and data sovereignty.

705 Decadal-scale climate projections provide information to guide adaptation efforts from continental-scale
706 national assessments down to regional levels. To ensure usability, those producing projections could consult
707 with users to determine the variables and timescales of interest to support efforts at appropriate spatial scales.
708 Consultations offer an opportunity for both information producers and users to understand the capabilities and
709 the limitations of the output. Model projection uncertainties, including internal, structural, and scenario
710 uncertainties, limit how output can be used. Care should be taken retain critical information and not create
711 misinformation by unrealistic assumptions about spatial and/or temporal averaging that overly generalize the
712 output. For example, a change in annual average precipitation across a 1000 km² watershed spanning 3,500 m
713 of elevation relief where annual precipitation varies by orders of magnitude and interannual variability is also
714 large provides little actionable information. Conversely, a projected average annual temperature change
715 resolved at high resolution (i.e., hourly output at 3 km² resolution) is equally inactionable when increases in
716 potentially dangerous extreme temperatures remain un-quantified. Iterative consultation and collaboration
717 between information producers and users—ideally incorporating an intermediary expert familiar with the
718 output and specific Tribal needs—can determine meaningful decision-relevant thresholds and appropriate

719 applications of information [118]. Examples of thresholds may include the number of days of maximum
720 temperature exceeding a threshold where legal requirements are invoked or trends in annual precipitation
721 derived from changes in extreme events. Thresholds can be identified and assessed across models, producing
722 a range of outcomes and a first-order estimate of certainty of these outcomes occurring by a given time
723 horizon [118]. These efforts benefit from well-defined timelines, expectations, and deliverables throughout
724 the project.

725 **3. Honor and include TEK, Tribal stewardship, and cultural practices in** 726 **government-to-government relationships and agreements.**

727 As TEK and Indigenous culture are deeply interwoven, traditional land management practices such as cultural
728 burning serve as an expression of this relationship [9, 10, 100]. Advisors indicated that both cultural and
729 prescribed fire activities must be implemented at larger scales and with greater frequency. However, current
730 implementation is hindered by varied limitations, from air quality-related regulations to agency staffing [16].
731 In particular, Advisors highlighted specific obstacles to implementing cultural burns, which are vital for
732 enhancing and maintaining ecocultural resources [16, 100]. To alleviate these barriers, Advisors expressed
733 opportunities for and value in partnerships with external jurisdictions and organizations based on reciprocal,
734 long-standing collaboration and information sharing [61].

735 Advisors suggested enhancing capacity-building for Tribal fire programs and fostering Indigenous-led or land
736 co-management opportunities. Coordinated fire response models, such as the California Fire and Rescue
737 Mutual Aid System, have increased local capacity by partnering directly with Tribal Fire Departments,
738 including those of the San Manuel, Barona, Viejas, and Pala Bands of Mission Indians [119, 120]. Several
739 partnerships have demonstrated approaches to integrating TEK and Western science. For instance, the Karuk
740 and Yurok Tribes have developed collaborative, community-based agreements with state and federal agencies
741 [16] that designate mutually-agreed upon Cultural Management Areas (CMAs) [56] and prioritize restoration
742 treatments based on Tribal ecological, social, cultural, and economic values [55, 121, 122]. Existing and
743 future efforts are not limited to fire. For instance, the North Coast Resource Partnership engages integrated,
744 multi-objective planning and project implementation (e.g., water conservation and storage, sediment
745 reduction, drought resiliency) across sovereign Tribal nations and local county governments within
746 California's North Coast [123]. However, co-management approaches have historically shown mixed results.
747 Even within co-management efforts that have worked towards integrating "Tribal ecocultural resource
748 objectives into management plans" [16], Tribes continue to experience a range of issues. These include co-
749 optation, unequal decision-making authority, and short-term, project-specific collaborations that undermine
750 long-term collaboration [56, 61, 100].

751 To move towards true co-management, literature proposes that non-Tribal agencies and landowners transition
752 from late-stage consultation to integrating Tribal perspectives at the outset of land management planning [4,
753 9, 63, 100]. In the fire context, true co-management can occur when agencies and Tribes share decision-
754 making authority to co-develop strategic cultural and prescribed fire plans that integrate Tribal knowledge,
755 perspectives, and ecological goals and jointly implement and/or monitor progress [4, 22, 100, 124]. Further,
756 external agencies can leverage Tribal liaisons to facilitate early-stage outreach and coordinate information
757 exchange along project timelines. However, Tribes have expressed barriers to and limitations in existing
758 consultation processes [8, 109]. The Tribal liaison role is often a minor part of an employee's full-time
759 position, and liaisons frequently support multiple Tribes [8]. Consequently, federal assessments with Tribal

760 officials have revealed that agencies initiate consultation too late in development cycles, fail to meaningfully
761 incorporate Tribal perspectives, and inadequately honor Tribal sovereignty and government-to-government
762 relationship dynamics [109].

763 Advisors called for meaningful government-to-government engagement wherein agencies educate staff
764 (Tribal Liaisons or otherwise) on Tribal engagement and values as defined by Tribes themselves to train build
765 trust and relational capacity while actively upholding Indigenous sovereignty [8, 56, 57, 64, 108, 125, 126].
766 One example includes participating in Fire Learning Networks to increase education and communication
767 around prescribed burning approaches that “blend traditional native burning with western science to restore
768 fire processes around communities where it is needed most” [55]. Another example is the potential formation
769 of dedicated stewardship training centers, which can serve both Indigenous peoples and partners across public
770 and private sectors through bidirectional learning modules that blend traditional fire stewardship with
771 standard fire suppression techniques, when determined appropriate by Tribes [4].

772 **4. Deepen local understanding of how past and future environmental changes** 773 **compound and cascade to impact Tribal lands and health.**

774 Advisors need included interagency, interdisciplinary assessments and mapping of the cascading effects of
775 weather and climate conditions on Tribal and surrounding lands. Integrated vulnerability and risk assessments
776 and subassessments that consider cascading or compounding events are essential for identifying both existing
777 and emerging risks. Assessments can include information on local vegetation, water resources, animal
778 species, and planned and implemented fuels management activities. Combined with knowledge sharing and
779 exchange (see Recommendation 1), comprehensive assessments of critical environmental and cultural assets-
780 at-risk will improve the capability of Tribes to plan for, adapt, and respond to variable environmental
781 conditions (see Themes 02 and 04) by guiding their risk assessments and adaptation priorities, “considering
782 strategies that achieve multiple objectives” [9].

783 To address these risks, working groups composed of Tribal (and non-Tribal) partners can develop initial
784 understandings of causes and effects, then include the broader public via a participatory process to refine [20]
785 while following FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and CARE (Collective benefit,
786 Authority to control, Responsibility, Ethics) Principles for Indigenous data governance [10, 63, 112, 127]. By
787 documenting events of interest, their immediate impacts, and potential cascading effects, such as community
788 responses and their effectiveness, documentation can be updated as outcomes are further identified and
789 understood. Ongoing updates can integrate concepts of adaptive management into documentation and ensure
790 they are pertinent to long-standing and more recent events and outcomes.

791 Documenting Tribally-relevant information and resources that integrate local observations and knowledge [9]
792 will help agencies engaged in formal agreements with Tribes to support Tribal information needs in ways that
793 balance interconnected ecological, social, economic, and safety priorities. Commitment to respect, reciprocity,
794 and responsibility are necessary for such collaboration [57]. Seeking Tribal consultation and/or IRB approval
795 is a standard prerequisite for such government-to-government engagement. These approvals are distinct for
796 each Tribe, functioning as governance mechanisms that enable Tribes to assert sovereignty and self-
797 determination, uphold ethical research standards, and safeguard community interests [128].

798 **5. Assess how weather warning systems reach Tribes, especially those with**
799 **dispersed remote populations.**

800 Multiple mechanisms (e.g., text messages, emails, briefings) provide varied ways to communicate upcoming
801 or ongoing hazardous conditions and the protective actions to take. Advisors expressed that, ideally, they
802 would receive inclement hazard notifications via text message sent by external agencies to Tribal leadership,
803 including environmental department leadership (Theme 07). Receiving notifications for each of their
804 geographic areas of concern with updates as conditions evolve was a wish list item.

805 To the extent possible, messaging disseminated at sufficient lead times can enable earlier preparations such as
806 moving resources (e.g., generators, fuel, and medicines) or people (pre-evacuation) ahead of upcoming
807 weather events, such as critical fire weather conditions that may impose Public Safety Power Shutoffs or
808 winter storms that may limit transportation accessibility [54]. Additional recommended actions include
809 creating a repository of alert systems that currently exist, to which Tribes could subscribe. This can include
810 the Federal Emergency Management Agency (FEMA) Integrated Public Alert and Warning System (IPAWS),
811 a tool that Tribal officials “can use to issue public alerts and warnings...to their jurisdiction” as “a single alert
812 simultaneously through multiple communication pathways”, including Wireless Emergency Alerts to cell
813 phones, Emergency Alert System to radio, satellite, and cable communications systems, and NOAA’s
814 Weather Radio [129].

815 **6. Co-produce training and guidance material for Tribal leaders to document**
816 **environmental extremes, risks, and outcomes.**

817 Advisors shared that Tribal leadership could benefit from training opportunities and guidance on documenting
818 environmental extremes, the risks they pose, and associated outcomes in terms of negative impacts and
819 recovery processes. They expressed needs for training and guidance materials intended for Tribal leaders
820 broadly and co-produced between Tribes and external agencies and organizations that integrate principles of
821 Tribal data sovereignty and leverage existing frameworks. Some external agencies and organizations have
822 created tutorials, trainings, and templates on documenting data in ways that respect Tribal sovereignty,
823 ensuring that Tribes retain authority over their data and knowledge [10, 61, 130]. Incorporating citizen
824 science approaches—such as those facilitated by the Local Environmental Observer Network, which connects
825 community observers and experts to share environmental event knowledge—can empower Tribes to both
826 receive alerts and contribute their own observations. Additionally, adapting “Lessons Learned”
827 documentation approaches like those of emergency management agencies [131, 132] but tailored to Tribal
828 contexts can support systematic reflection on impacts and recoveries. This combined approach facilitates
829 comprehensive documentation of impacts and lessons learned and honors Indigenous governance.

830 **7. Co-produce training and outreach materials with Tribal leaders to help them**
831 **easily share environmental information within their communities.**

832 Advisors expressed a need for more accessible and interpretable environmental information from other
833 agencies and organizations to support Tribal leaderships’ decision-making and communication to Tribal
834 citizens. To meet this need, agencies and organizations collaborating with Tribal communities
835 (Recommendation 4) can co-produce and offer accessible training, templates, and outreach materials [133].
836 These resources, including visualizations and audience-specific communication templates, can be tailored to

837 local contexts through storytelling [134] and relevant visual formats derived from identification of shared
838 values, norms or beliefs [135, 136] while respecting Tribal sovereignty and self-determination. Templates and
839 outreach material can be developed across the hazard management cycle, including for environmental
840 vulnerability assessments and adaptation planning (Recommendation 2), hazard response (Recommendation
841 5), and recovery (Recommendation 6). This recommendation complements existing guides and toolkits for
842 Tribal adaptation planning and hazard mitigation [126, 137, 138] centering on approaches for Tribal
843 leadership to communicate environmental information before, during, and after extreme events. It also
844 characterizes specific risks to Tribal communities by flexibly allowing Tribal leadership to integrate TEK and
845 oral histories with environmental data. Last, outreach products that bridge risk communication and health
846 literacy can enhance the capacity for taking protective action [139] presumably improving health outcomes
847 and reducing burdens on healthcare systems.

848 **Limitations**

849 Several limitations warrant consideration when interpreting our findings. While we purposively sampled
850 Advisors based on their TCHP TAB involvement, this constrained our sample size with at least three
851 implications. First, our sample size of 10 interview Advisors is a fraction of the 171 Tribal communities in
852 California, implying we undersampled the varied environmental conditions and exposures of concern.
853 Second, many California-based Tribes do not have access to their ancestral coastal territories. Here, few
854 coastal Tribes were sampled, implying perspectives on coastal hazards (e.g., tsunamis, erosion, water quality,
855 and sea level rise) were limited. Third, the limited sample size represents only a fraction of the roles and
856 experiences of Tribal environmental professionals. Thus, Tribal perspectives were limited to the views of the
857 individual environmental professionals we interviewed, which may not reflect the broader views or
858 experiences of their Tribe nor California Tribes writ large.

859 The themes were influenced by both the composition of our team and our collaborative development of
860 research materials [59, 60, 95]. We acknowledge that our own identities, and the biases therein, partially
861 shaped the themes we generated. Additionally, thematic analyses were conducted and reported as they
862 pertained to the entire Advisor group. While some findings pertained more specifically to certain Tribes, we
863 did not attribute such findings to those specific Tribes to preserve anonymity. To further mitigate bias and
864 ensure Tribal views were accurately represented, we incorporated feedback from Advisors who were willing
865 and able to optionally and voluntarily review our findings to help ensure that findings resonated with Advisor
866 perspectives [74].

867 **Conclusions**

868 Seven themes pertaining to needs surrounding planning, response, and recovery to long-term environmental
869 change and both singular and complex extreme events emerged from semi-structured interviews with 10
870 California Tribal Environmental professionals. To support adaptation efforts, funding agencies and applicants
871 may consider the lifecycle of activities (i.e., from training to long-term maintenance) associated with these
872 efforts, rather than only the specific intervention. Making public data accessible and usable, especially for
873 Tribal professionals and leadership, will facilitate planning and measuring outcomes of adaptation efforts.
874 Honoring and elevating Tribal perspectives and customs in agreements may improve relationships between
875 entities and deepen understanding of how Tribes and other communities are impacted by, respond to, and
876 recover from adverse events. This could facilitate producing training and other outreach materials enabling
877 Tribal leadership to more effectively communicate information to their communities during rapidly unfolding

878 events, when timeliness and mechanisms of communication are paramount. It will also help during slower-to-
879 unfold events, when long-term documentation helps maintain information continuity as projects evolve.
880 Documenting how events affected communities and the lessons learned will increase the effectiveness of
881 future interventions. Frequent engagement and trust-building between various entities will drive progress on
882 addressing these themes. By summarizing themes into actionable recommendations (Table 2) this work
883 intends to benefit all partners and enhance broader-scale community resilience.

884 Building on our exploratory findings, additional research can further adapt our recommendations to improve
885 environmental information and communication tools with Tribal communities while ensuring that cultural
886 context and knowledge sensitivities are respected. Collaborative efforts should focus on integrating Tribal
887 end-user insights into the design of resources. Resources could include training materials, educational
888 curricula, data clearinghouses, and decision-support tools, such as for the TCHP's Exposures, Impacts, and
889 Strategies Inventory [138] or environmental warning products. Further research is needed to illuminate how
890 Tribes self-determine adaptation actions, evaluate project selection criteria, and measure adaptation
891 outcomes[60]. Additionally, future evaluations of new and existing tools should consider how the needs and
892 decision-making processes of Tribal personnel can be addressed to ensure these resources are useful across
893 decision making environments [140-142]. Continuous engagement with Tribal professionals to assess,
894 evaluate, and iteratively improve these resources will ensure these efforts are increasingly successful.

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904 **Supporting Information**

905 **S1 Appendix. Historical California (2013 - 2026) Hazard Events Informing Figure 1.**

906 **S2 Appendix. Semi-structured Interview Guide.**

907 **S3 Appendix. Interview Summary Template.**

908 **S4 Appendix. Codebook.**

909 **S5 Checklist. Inclusivity in Global Research.**

910 **References**

911

912 1. Fillmore H, Singletary L. Climate data and information needs of indigenous communities on
913 reservation lands: insights from stakeholders in the Southwestern United States. *Climatic Change*.
914 2021;169(3):37.

- 915 2. Ellis R, Perry D. A confluence of anticolonial pathways for indigenous sacred site protection. *Journal*
916 *of Contemporary Water Research & Education*. 2020;169(1):8-26.
- 917 3. Maldonado J, Bennett TB, Chief K, Cochran P, Cozzetto K, Gough B, et al. Engagement with
918 indigenous peoples and honoring traditional knowledge systems. *The US National Climate Assessment:*
919 *innovations in science and engagement*: Springer; 2015. p. 111-26.
- 920 4. Hankins DL. Climate resilience through ecocultural stewardship. *Proceedings of the National*
921 *Academy of Sciences*. 2024;121(32):e2310072121.
- 922 5. Whyte K. Indigenous science (fiction) for the Anthropocene: Ancestral dystopias and fantasies of
923 climate change crises. *nvironment and Planning E: Nature and Space*., 2018;1(1):224 - 42.
- 924 6. Jantarasami L, Novak R, Delgado R, Marino E, McNeeley S, Narducci C, et al. Tribes and indigenous
925 peoples. *Impacts, risks, and adaptation in the United States: Fourth national climate assessment*.
926 2018;2(15):572-603.
- 927 7. Mayer B, Joshweseoma L, Sehongva G. Environmental risk perceptions and community health:
928 Arsenic, air pollution, and threats to traditional values of the Hopi Tribe. *Journal of community health*.
929 2019;44(5):896-902.
- 930 8. Whyte K, Novak R, Laramie M, Bruscatto N, David-Chavez D, Dockry M, et al. Ch. 16. Tribes and
931 Indigenous Peoples. Washington, DC: US Global Change Research Program, 2023.
- 932 9. Status of Tribes and Climate Change Working Group. *Status of Tribes and Climate Change*. Flagstaff
933 (AZ): Northern Arizona University Institute for Tribal Environmental Professionals, 2021.
- 934 10. Status of Tribes and Climate Change Working Group. *Status of Tribes and Climate Change*. Flagstaff
935 (AZ): Northern Arizona University Institute for Tribal Environmental Professionals, 2025.
- 936 11. Stanley LR, Swaim RC, Kaholokula JKa, Kelly KJ, Belcourt A, Allen J. The imperative for research
937 to promote health equity in indigenous communities. *Prevention Science*. 2020;21(Suppl 1):13-21.
- 938 12. Donatuto J, Grossman E, Konovsky J, Grossman S, Campbell L. Indigenous community health and
939 climate change: integrating biophysical and social science indicators. *Coastal Management*. 2014;42(4):355 -
940 73. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/08920753.2014.923140>.
- 941 13. Long JW, Steel EA. Shifting perspectives in assessing socio-environmental vulnerability.
942 *Sustainability*. 2020;12(7):2625.
- 943 14. Tribal Resilience Action Database. *Climate Resilience Actions*. In: Foundation USRT, Tribes UCU,
944 Commission CRI-TF, International A, editors. 2025.
- 945 15. Cajete GA. Indigenous science, climate change, and indigenous community building: A framework of
946 foundational perspectives for indigenous community resilience and revitalization. *Sustainability*.
947 2020;12(22):9569.
- 948 16. Marks-Block T, Lake FK, Curran LM. Effects of understory fire management treatments on
949 California Hazelnut, an ecocultural resource of the Karuk and Yurok Indians in the Pacific Northwest. *Forest*
950 *Ecology and Management*. 2019;450:117517.
- 951 17. Dettinger MD, Ralph FM, Das T, Neiman PJ, Cayan DR. Atmospheric rivers, floods and the water
952 resources of California. *Water*. 2011;3(2):445-78.

- 953 18. Indigenous Peoples Burning Network. Fact Sheet. Fire Networks, 2024.
- 954 19. Tribal EcoRestoration Alliance. Our work 2025 [cited 2025]. Available from:
955 <https://www.tribalecorestoration.org/our-work>.
- 956 20. Cultural Fire Management Council. About us Weitchpec (CA)n.d. [cited 2025]. Available from:
957 <https://www.culturalfire.org/about>.
- 958 21. Huntington S, Wise P. Native nations respond to Los Angeles fires. IndiJ Public Media. 2025 January
959 14, 2025.
- 960 22. Adams MM. Indigenous fire data sovereignty: Applying indigenous data sovereignty principles to fire
961 research. *Fire*. 2024;7(7):222.
- 962 23. National Centers for Environmental Information. Storm Data Publication Asheville (NC): National
963 Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration; 2025 [cited 2025].
- 964 24. Lund J. California's Agricultural and Urban Water Supply Reliability and the Sacramento–San
965 Joaquin Delta. *San Francisco Estuary and Watershed Science*. 2016;14(3). doi:
966 10.15447/sfews.2016v14iss3art6.
- 967 25. Delta Independent Science Board. Water Quality Science in the Sacramento–San Joaquin Delta:
968 Chemical Contaminants and Nutrients. Sacramento (CA): Delta Stewardship Council, 2018.
- 969 26. Hartman R, Knowles N, Fencel A, Ekstrom J. Drought in the Delta: Socio-ecological Impacts,
970 Responses, and Tools. *San Francisco Estuary and Watershed Science*. 2025;23(1). doi:
971 10.15447/sfews.2025v23iss1art3.
- 972 27. Gershunov A, Hatchett B, Weyant A, Dettinger M, Su L, Rhoades A, et al. Atmospheric Rivers and
973 Floods in California's Changing Hydroclimate. *San Francisco Estuary and Watershed Science*. 2025;23(3).
974 doi: 10.15447/sfews.2025v23iss3art3.
- 975 28. Mahardja B, Bashevkin S, Pien C, Khanna S, Pearson D, Davis B, et al. Heatwaves and Rising
976 Temperatures in the Upper San Francisco Estuary: Trends and Effects on Ecosystems and Humans. *San*
977 *Francisco Estuary and Watershed Science*. 2025;23(1). doi: 10.15447/sfews.2025v23iss1art4.
- 978 29. Reed CC, Hood SM, Cluck DR, Smith SL. Fuels change quickly after California drought and bark
979 beetle outbreaks with implications for potential fire behavior and emissions. *Fire Ecology*. 2023;19(1). doi:
980 10.1186/s42408-023-00175-6.
- 981 30. Stephens SL, Bernal AA, Collins BM, Finney MA, Lautenberger C, Saah D. Mass fire behavior
982 created by extensive tree mortality and high tree density not predicted by operational fire behavior models in
983 the southern Sierra Nevada. *Forest Ecology and Management*. 2022;518:120258.
- 984 31. Axelson J, Battles J, Bulaon B, Cluck D, Cousins S, Cox L, et al. The California Tree Mortality Data
985 Collection Network — Enhanced communication and collaboration among scientists and stakeholders.
986 *California Agriculture*. 2019;73(2):55-62. doi: 10.3733/ca.2019a0001.
- 987 32. Asner GP, Brodrick PG, Anderson CB, Vaughn N, Knapp DE, Martin RE. Progressive forest canopy
988 water loss during the 2012–2015 California drought. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*.
989 2016;113(2):E249-E55. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1523397113.

- 990 33. Keeley JE, Syphard AD. Twenty-first century California, USA, wildfires: fuel-dominated vs. wind-
991 dominated fires. *Fire Ecology*. 2019;15(1):24.
- 992 34. United States Department of Agriculture Forest Service Region 5. Aerial Detection Monitoring
993 [Internet] Vallejo (CA): United States Department of Agriculture; 2025 [cited 2025 November]. Available
994 from: <https://www.fs.usda.gov/r05/natural-resources/forest-health/aerial-detection-monitoring>.
- 995 35. Safford HD, Saberi S. Fuel treatment effects on fire severity during the Caldor Fire (2021), Lake
996 Tahoe, California, USA. *Forest Ecology and Management*. 2026;603:123424.
- 997 36. National Integrated Drought Information System. Snow Drought Drought.gov: National Oceanic and
998 Atmospheric Administration; [cited 2025]. Available from: [https://www.drought.gov/what-is-drought/snow-](https://www.drought.gov/what-is-drought/snow-drought)
999 [drought](https://www.drought.gov/what-is-drought/snow-drought).
- 1000 37. Rhoades AM, North J, Rudisill W, Hatchett B, Risser M, Beltran-Pena A, et al. Snow-eater
1001 heatwaves of the western United States. 2026.
- 1002 38. Carreras-Sospedra M, Zhu S, Mackinnon M, Lassman W, Mirocha JD, Barbato M, et al. Air quality
1003 and health impacts of the 2020 wildfires in California. *Fire Ecology*. 2024;20(1). doi: 10.1186/s42408-023-
1004 00234-y.
- 1005 39. Schollaert C, Connolly R, Cushing L, Jerrett M, Liu T, Marlier M. Air quality impacts of the January
1006 2025 Los Angeles wildfires: Insights from public data sources. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*.
1007 2025;12(8):911-7.
- 1008 40. Thomas MA, Lindsay DN, Kean JW, Graber AP, Rossi RK, Kostelnik J, et al. Landsliding follows
1009 signatures of wildfire history and vegetation regrowth in a steep coastal shrubland. *Geosphere*.
1010 2025;21(5):823-40. doi: 10.1130/ges02856.1.
- 1011 41. Guirguis K, Hatchett B, Clemesha R, Aguilera R, Gershunov A, Campbell I, et al. Compound
1012 atmospheric drivers of the catastrophic 2025 Los Angeles urban firestorm. *npj Natural Hazards*. 2025;2(1).
1013 doi: 10.1038/s44304-025-00155-7.
- 1014 42. Cayan DR, Dehaan LL, Gershunov A, Guzman-Morales J, Keeley JE, Mumford J, et al. Autumn
1015 precipitation: the competition with Santa Ana winds in determining fire outcomes in southern California.
1016 *International Journal of Wildland Fire*. 2022;31(11):1056-67. doi: 10.1071/wf22065.
- 1017 43. Tardy A. Tropical cyclone Kay remnant moisture and Tropical Storm Hilary landfall with flash
1018 flooding, and debris flows in Southern California. 104th Annual AMS Meeting 2024; January 01, 2024;
1019 Baltimore, MD2024. p. 430973.
- 1020 44. Dow HW, Warrick JA, Ritchie AC. Patterns and Drivers of Cliff Erosion in Big Sur, California, USA
1021 Using Repeat Photogrammetry, 2017–2023. *Earth and Space Science*. 2026;13(5). doi:
1022 10.1029/2025ea004595.
- 1023 45. Hatchett BJ, Cao Q, Dawson PB, Ellis CJ, Hecht CW, Kawzenuk B, et al. Observations of an
1024 Extreme Atmospheric River Storm With a Diverse Sensor Network. *Earth and Space Science*. 2020;7(8). doi:
1025 10.1029/2020ea001129.
- 1026 46. Segura RL, Stewart IT, DeCosse DE, Young ER, Young ST, Tatum P, et al. A multidisciplinary
1027 approach to understanding vulnerability and building climate resilience to levee failures and flooding in
1028 historically marginalized communities. *Journal of Environmental Studies and Sciences*. 2025:1-17.

- 1029 47. Hatchett BJ, Nauslar NJ, Brown TJ. Comparing ground-based lightning detection networks near
1030 wildfire points-of-origin. *Natural Hazards*. 2024;120(14):13617-26. doi: 10.1007/s11069-024-06741-8.
- 1031 48. National Drought Mitigation Center. United States Drought Monitor: Time Series. In: Center NDM,
1032 editor. University of Nebraska-Lincoln 2025.
- 1033 49. Curtis JA, Johnson GS, Cahill JD, Genzoli L, Dahm CN, Schenk LN, et al. 2022 McKinney rain-on-
1034 wildfire event, dissolved oxygen sags, and a fish kill on the Klamath River, California. *Scientific Reports*.
1035 2025;15(1). doi: 10.1038/s41598-025-08179-9.
- 1036 50. Free CM, Anderson SC, Hellmers EA, Muhling BA, Navarro MO, Richerson K, et al. Impact of the
1037 2014–2016 marine heatwave on US and Canada West Coast fisheries: Surprises and lessons from key case
1038 studies. *Fish and Fisheries*. 2023;24(4):652-74. doi: 10.1111/faf.12753.
- 1039 51. Sabal MC, Richerson K, Moran P, Levi T, Tuttle VJ, Banks M. Warm oceans exacerbate Chinook
1040 salmon bycatch in the Pacific hake fishery driven by thermal and diel depth-use behaviours. *Fish and*
1041 *Fisheries*. 2023;24(6):910-23. doi: 10.1111/faf.12775.
- 1042 52. Diver S, Eitzel M, Brown M, Hazel A, Reed R, Fricke S. Indigenous nations at the confluence: water
1043 governance networks and system transformation in the Klamath Basin. *Ecology and Society*. 2022;27(4). doi:
1044 10.5751/es-12942-270404.
- 1045 53. Fitzpatrick KM. The "upside-down" river: Trends in total nitrogen, total phosphorus, and microcystin
1046 concentration in the Klamath Basin, 2010-2021. 2024.
- 1047 54. Bamford E, Parker B, Shiple M, Weight E, M W. NIDIS Tribal Drought Engagement Strategy 2021-
1048 2025: For the Missouri River Basin and Midwest Drought Early Warning Systems. National Oceanic and
1049 Atmospheric Administration National Integrated Drought Information System, 2020.
- 1050 55. United States Department of Agriculture. Some Bar Integrated Fire Management Project: Draft
1051 environmental assessment. In: Service F, editor. Six Rivers National Forest 2018.
- 1052 56. Diver S. Co-management as a catalyst: pathways to post-colonial forestry in the Klamath Basin,
1053 California. *Human Ecology*. 2016;44(5):533-46.
- 1054 57. Jennings MK, Pairis A, Walker A, Madrigal W, Terry D, Tamm J, et al. Climate Transformation and
1055 Stewardship: Reflections on Meaningful Collaboration to Support Indigenous-Led Research. *Ecology and*
1056 *Evolution*. 2025;15(12). doi: 10.1002/ece3.72715.
- 1057 58. Hasert R, Countryman C, Marchand A, Poe M, Avery K, Krosby M. Climate Adaptation Barriers and
1058 Needs Experienced by Northwest Coastal Tribes: Key Findings from Tribal Listening Sessions. University of
1059 Washington Climate Impacts Group, Affiliated Tribes of Northwest Indians, Washington Sea Grant, 2024.
- 1060 59. Copes-Gerbitz K, Hagerman SM, Daniels LD. Situating Indigenous knowledge for resilience in fire-
1061 dependent socioecological systems. *Ecology & Society*. 2021;26(4).
- 1062 60. Herbert N, Beckman C, Vera K, Coles E, Kim T, Cho S-H, et al. Bridging incremental to
1063 transformative hazard management strategies on the Tule River Indian Reservation. *Environmental Research:*
1064 *Health*. 2025;3(1):011002.

- 1065 61. Yazzie K, Craig D, Lynn K, Whyte K, Cooley N, Cozzetto K, et al. Improving Climate Services for
1066 Tribes: Recommendations from a National Survey of Service Users and Providers. *Bulletin of the American*
1067 *Meteorological Society*. 2026;107(2):E277-E90. doi: 10.1175/bams-d-24-0182.1.
- 1068 62. Jennings L, Jones K, Taitingfong R, Martinez A, David-Chavez D, Alegado R', et al. Governance of
1069 Indigenous data in open earth systems science. *Nature communications*. 2025;16(1):572.
- 1070 63. Carroll S, Garba I, Figueroa-Rodríguez O, Holbrook J, Lovett R, Materechera S, et al. The CARE
1071 principles for indigenous data governance. *Data science journal*. 2020;19.
- 1072 64. David-Chavez D, Ferguson DB, Curley A, Lane T, Yazzie S, Leroy S, et al. Policy Brief: Supporting
1073 Tribal Data Governance for Indigenous Community Climate Resilience. Tucson: University of Arizona
1074 Native Nations Institute and the Climate Assessment for the Southwest, 2019.
- 1075 65. Wilkinson M, Dumontier M, Aalbersberg J, Appleton G, Axton M, Baak A, et al. The FAIR Guiding
1076 Principles for scientific data management and stewardship. *Scientific data*. 2016;3(1):1-9.
- 1077 66. Tribal Climate Health Project. About the Tribal Climate Health Project 2025 [cited 2025]. Available
1078 from: <https://tribalclimatehealth.org/about/>.
- 1079 67. Altschuld JW, Watkins R. A primer on needs assessment: More than 40 years of research and
1080 practice. *New Directions for Evaluation*. 2014;2014(144):5-18.
- 1081 68. Haverland A, Garfin G. Toward Effective Actionable Science: Stakeholder Needs Assessment Final
1082 Report. Institute of the Environment. University of Arizona; 2019.
- 1083 69. Braun V, Clarke V. To saturate or not to saturate? Questioning data saturation as a useful concept for
1084 thematic analysis and sample-size rationales. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise and health*.
1085 2021;13(2):201-16.
- 1086 70. Akhter S. Key informants' interviews. *Principles of social research methodology*: Springer; 2022. p.
1087 389-403.
- 1088 71. Hicks N, Millar RJ, Girling LM, Cummins PA, Yamashita T. Conducting Virtual Qualitative
1089 Interviews with International Key Informants: Insights from a Research Project. *Grantee Submission*.
1090 2021;26(9):2857-71.
- 1091 72. Carabine E. Revitalising evidence-based policy for the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk
1092 Reduction 2015-2030: lessons from existing international science partnerships. *PLoS currents*.
1093 2015;7:ecurrents. dis. aab45b2b4106307ae2168a485e03b8a.
- 1094 73. Kumar K. Conducting key informant interviews in developing countries: Agency for International
1095 Development Washington DC; 1989.
- 1096 74. Chief K, Meadow A, Whyte K. Engaging southwestern tribes in sustainable water resources topics
1097 and management. *Water*. 2016;8(8):350.
- 1098 75. Gittelsohn J, Belcourt A, Magarati M, Booth-LaForce C, Duran B, Mishra SI, et al. Building capacity
1099 for productive indigenous community-university partnerships. *Prevention Science*. 2020;21(Suppl 1):22-32.
- 1100 76. Adams WC. Conducting semi-structured interviews. *Handbook of practical program evaluation*.
1101 2015:492-505.

- 1102 77. Kallio H, Pietilä AM, Johnson M, Kangasniemi M. Systematic methodological review: developing a
1103 framework for a qualitative semi-structured interview guide. *Journal of advanced nursing*. 2016;72(12):2954-
1104 65.
- 1105 78. Vickery J, Atkinson P, Lin L, Rubin O, Upshur R, Yeoh E, et al. Challenges to evidence-informed
1106 decision-making in the context of pandemics: qualitative study of COVID-19 policy advisor perspectives.
1107 *BMJ Global Health*. 2022;7(4).
- 1108 79. McKim C. Meaningful Member-Checking: A Structured Approach to Member-Checking. *American*
1109 *Journal of Qualitative Research*. 2023;7(2):41 - 52.
- 1110 80. Varpio L, Ajjawi R, Monrouxe L, O'Brien B, Rees C. Shedding the cobra effect: problematising
1111 thematic emergence, triangulation, saturation and member checking. *Medical education*,. 2016;5(1):40-50.
1112 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1111/medu.13124>.
- 1113 81. VERBI Software. MAXQDA. 2025.
- 1114 82. Knott E, Rao AH, Summers K, Teeger C. Interviews in the social sciences. *Nature Reviews Methods*
1115 *Primers*. 2022;2(1):73.
- 1116 83. Braun V, Clarke V. Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative research in psychology*.
1117 2006;3(2):77-101.
- 1118 84. Patton M. *Qualitative Evaluation and Research Methods*. 2 ed: SAGE Publications, Inc.; 1990.
- 1119 85. Morss RE, Vickery J, Lazrus H, Demuth J, Bostrom A. Improving tropical cyclone forecast
1120 communication by understanding NWS partners' decision timelines and forecast information needs. *Weather,*
1121 *Climate, and Society*. 2022;14(3):783-800.
- 1122 86. Miles MB, Huberman AM, Saldana J. *Qualitative Data Analysis: A Methods Sourcebook*: SAGE
1123 Publications, Inc; 2019.
- 1124 87. Thompson J. A guide to abductive thematic analysis. *The qualitative report*. 2022;27(5):1410-21.
- 1125 88. Khurshid F, Veen M, Thompson J, Hegazi I. Navigating Thematic Analysis: Practical Strategies
1126 Grounded in Abductive Reasoning. *Teaching and Learning in Medicine*. 2026;38(1):106-15. doi:
1127 10.1080/10401334.2025.2475098.
- 1128 89. Saldaña J. *The Coding Manual for Qualitative Researchers*. 3 ed: SAGE Publications Ltd; 2015.
- 1129 90. Brennan RL, Prediger DJ. Coefficient kappa: Some uses, misuses, and alternatives. *Educational and*
1130 *psychological measurement*. 1981;41(3):687-99.
- 1131 91. Landis JR, Koch GG. The measurement of observer agreement for categorical data. *biometrics*.
1132 1977:159-74.
- 1133 92. Cohen J. A coefficient of agreement for nominal scales. *Educational and psychological measurement*.
1134 1960;20(1):37-46.
- 1135 93. Campbell JL, Quincy C, Osserman J, Pedersen OK. Coding in-depth semistructured interviews:
1136 Problems of unitization and intercoder reliability and agreement. *Sociological methods & research*.
1137 2013;42(3):294-320.

- 1138 94. Braun V, Clarke V. Reflecting on reflexive thematic analysis. *Qualitative research in sport, exercise*
1139 *and health*. 2019;11(4):589-97.
- 1140 95. Savin-Baden M, Major CH. *Personal stance, positionality, and reflexivity. Qualitative research: the*
1141 *essential guide to theory and practice*. 1 ed. London: Routledge; 2023.
- 1142 96. Thoreson J, McCovey K, Rossier C, Lake FK, Hajjar R, Hillman CC, et al. Monitoring of black oak
1143 (*xánthiip*) to center indigenous ecocultural revitalization. *Earth Stewardship*. 2024;1(1). doi:
1144 10.1002/eas2.70002.
- 1145 97. Mehlretter S, Longboat S, Luby B, Bradford A. *Indigenous and Western knowledge: Bringing*
1146 *diverse understandings of water together in practice*. Global Commission on the Economics of Water. 2023.
- 1147 98. Kovach M. *Indigenous methodologies: Characteristics, conversations, and contexts*: University of
1148 Toronto press; 2021.
- 1149 99. Elias EH, Flynn R, Idowu OJ, Reyes J, Sanogo S, Schutte BJ, et al. Crop vulnerability to weather and
1150 climate risk: Analysis of interacting systems and adaptation efficacy for sustainable crop production.
1151 *Sustainability*. 2019;11(23):6619.
- 1152 100. Clark S, Tripp B, Hankins D, Rossier CE, Varney A, Nairn I. *Good Fire II: Current Barriers to the*
1153 *Expansion of Cultural Burning and Prescribed Fire Use in the United States and Recommended Solutions*.
1154 The Karuk Tribe, 2024.
- 1155 101. Martin C, Doyle J, LaFrance J, Lefthand MJ, Young SL, Three Irons E, et al. Change rippling
1156 through our waters and culture. *Journal of Contemporary Water Research & Education*. 2020;169(1):61-78.
- 1157 102. Fillmore H. Using the Washoe Language to Inform Hydrologic and Environmental Models. *Ground*
1158 *Water*. 2017;55(5).
- 1159 103. Pascual U, Balvanera P, Díaz S, Pataki G, Roth E, Stenseke M, et al. Valuing nature's contributions
1160 to people: the IPBES approach. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*. 2017;26:7-16.
- 1161 104. Burnette CE, Clark CB, Rodning CB. "Living off the land": How subsistence promotes well-being
1162 and resilience among indigenous peoples of the Southeastern United States. *Social Service Review*.
1163 2018;92(3):369-400.
- 1164 105. Yavaş N. Staging Relational Ethics: Salmon Is Everything as Ritual Performance. *Litera: Journal of*
1165 *Language, Literature and Culture Studies*. 2025;35(2):348-65.
- 1166 106. Jones GM, Thompson C, Sawyer SC, Norman KE, Parks SA, Hayes TM, et al. Conserving landscape
1167 dynamics, not just landscapes. *BioScience*. 2025;75(5):409-15. doi: 10.1093/biosci/biaf023.
- 1168 107. Lynn K, Daigle J, Hoffman J, Lake F, Michelle N, Ranco D, et al. The impacts of climate change on
1169 tribal traditional foods. *Climate change and Indigenous peoples in the United States: Impacts, experiences*
1170 *and actions*: Springer; 2013. p. 37-48.
- 1171 108. Fisk JJ, Leong KM, Berl REW, Long JW, Landon AC, Adams MM, et al. Evolving wildlife
1172 management cultures of governance through Indigenous Knowledges and perspectives. *The Journal of*
1173 *Wildlife Management*. 2024;88(6). doi: 10.1002/jwmg.22584.
- 1174 109. United States Government Accountability Office. *Tribal consultation: Additional federal actions*
1175 *needed for infrastructure projects*. 2019.

1176 110. Long JW, Lake FK. Escaping social-ecological traps through tribal stewardship on national forest
1177 lands in the Pacific Northwest, United States of America. *Ecology and Society*. 2018;23(2). doi: 10.5751/es-
1178 10041-230210.

1179 111. Jessen TD, Ban NC, Claxton NX, Darimont CT. Contributions of Indigenous Knowledge to
1180 ecological and evolutionary understanding. *Frontiers in Ecology and the Environment*. 2022;20(2):93-101.
1181 doi: 10.1002/fee.2435.

1182 112. Carroll SR, Herczog E, Hudson M, Russell K, Stall S. Operationalizing the CARE and FAIR
1183 Principles for Indigenous data futures. *Scientific data*. 2021;8(1):108.

1184 113. Garba I, Sterling R, Plevel R, Carson W, Cordova-Marks FM, Cummins J, et al. Indigenous peoples
1185 and research: self-determination in research governance. *Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics*.
1186 2023;8:1272318.

1187 114. Collins M, Hatchett BJ, Tonino S, Zhou Y, Hur NJ. Report-Backs: A customizable science
1188 communication “model” for reporting results to participatory science observers. *Bulletin of the American
1189 Meteorological Society*. 2025:BAMS-D-24-0142.1.

1190 115. Southwest Ecological Restoration Institutes. ReSHAPE Treatment and Wildfire Interagency
1191 Geodatabase (TWIG) Viewer: Data Layers: Northern Arizona University, Colorado State University, New
1192 Mexico Highlands University; [cited 2026]. Available from: <https://reshapewildfire.org/twig/layers>.

1193 116. WIFIRE Lab. WIFIRE San Diego (CA): San Diego Supercomputing Center; [cited 2026]. Available
1194 from: <https://wifire-data.sdsc.edu/>.

1195 117. Magee J, Gurule S, Echo-Hawk A. Decolonizing Data. In: Urban Indian Health Institute SIHB,
1196 editor. 2023.

1197 118. Oakley NS, Hatchett BJ, McEvoy DJ, Rodrigues L. Projected changes in Ventura County Climate.
1198 Reno (NV): Western Regional Climate Center Desert Research Institute, 2019.

1199 119. State Launches Historic Firefighting Partnership with the Pala Band of Mission Indians [Internet]. Cal
1200 OES News; 2023 [cited February 1, 2025]. Available from: [https://news.caloes.ca.gov/state-launches-historic-
1201 firefighting-partnership-with-the-pala-band-of-mission-indians/](https://news.caloes.ca.gov/state-launches-historic-firefighting-partnership-with-the-pala-band-of-mission-indians/)

1202 120. Ahead of peak wildfire season, state adds Barona and Viejas Fire Departments to California Fire and
1203 Rescue Mutual Aid System [Internet]. Cal OES News; 2024 [cited February 1, 2025]. Available from:
1204 [https://news.caloes.ca.gov/ahead-of-peak-wildfire-season-state-adds-barona-and-viejas-fire-departments-to-
1205 california-fire-and-rescue-mutual-aid-system/](https://news.caloes.ca.gov/ahead-of-peak-wildfire-season-state-adds-barona-and-viejas-fire-departments-to-california-fire-and-rescue-mutual-aid-system/)

1206 121. Western Klamath Restoration Partnership. Who we are 2025 [cited 2025]. Available from:
1207 <https://www.wkrp.network/>.

1208 122. Nairn C. Tribe and partners light up a forest to restore landscape in California. *Mongabay*. 2022 Nov
1209 8.

1210 123. North Coast Resource Partnership. A Strategy for Enhancing Long Term Capacity in Tribal and Rural
1211 Fire Agencies in the North Coast Region. 2024.

1212 124. Wildland Fire Mitigation and Management Commission. ON FIRE: The Report of the Wildland Fire
1213 Mitigation and Management Commission. Agriculture USDo; 2023.

- 1214 125. Sutherland WJ, Burgess ND, Edwards SV, Jones JPG, Soltis PS, Tilman D, et al. Nine changes
1215 needed to deliver a radical transformation in biodiversity measurement. *Proceedings of the National Academy*
1216 *of Sciences*. 2026;123(10). doi: 10.1073/pnas.2519345123.
- 1217 126. Dalton M, Hatfield S, Petersen A, Russell N, Basaraba A, Bisett D. *Tribal Climate Adaptation*
1218 *Guidebook: About*: Oregon Climate Change Research Institute,
1219 Adaptation International; 2022 [cited 2025 March 1]. Available from:
1220 <https://tribalclimateadaptationguidebook.org/about/>.
- 1221 127. Jennings L, Anderson T, Martinez A, Sterling R, Chavez DD, Garba I, et al. Applying the ‘CARE
1222 Principles for Indigenous Data Governance’ to ecology and biodiversity research. *Nature ecology & evolution*.
1223 2023;7(10):1547-51.
- 1224 128. Harding A, Harper B, Stone D, O’Neill C, Berger P, Harris S, et al. Conducting research with tribal
1225 communities: Sovereignty, ethics, and data-sharing issues. *Environmental health perspectives*. 2012;120(1):6-
1226 10.
- 1227 129. Federal Emergency Management Agency. *How Tribal Nations Can Implement IPAWS to send Public*
1228 *Alerts & Warnings*. FEMA, 2022.
- 1229 130. Native Nations Institute. *Rebuilding Native Nations Online Course Tucson (AZ)*: University of
1230 Arizona; [cited 2025]. Available from: [https://nni.arizona.edu/our-work/education-professional-](https://nni.arizona.edu/our-work/education-professional-development/rebuilding-native-nations-online)
1231 [development/rebuilding-native-nations-online](https://nni.arizona.edu/our-work/education-professional-development/rebuilding-native-nations-online).
- 1232 131. White M, Cohan A. *A Guide to Capturing Lessons Learned*. The Nature Conservancy, n.d.
- 1233 132. Wildland Fire Lessons Learned Center. *Wildland Fire Lessons Learned Center 2025*. Available from:
1234 <https://lessons.fs2c.usda.gov/>.
- 1235 133. VanderMolen K, Kimutis N, Hatchett BJ. Recommendations for increasing the reach and
1236 effectiveness of heat risk education and warning messaging. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*.
1237 2022;82:103288.
- 1238 134. Fernández-Llamazares Á, Cabeza M. Rediscovering the potential of indigenous storytelling for
1239 conservation practice. *Conservation Letters*. 2018;11(3):e12398.
- 1240 135. Lambrecht K, Hatchett BJ, VanderMolen K, Feldkircher B. Identifying community values related to
1241 heat: recommendations for forecast and health risk communication. *Geoscience Communication*.
1242 2021;4(4):517-25. doi: 10.5194/gc-4-517-2021.
- 1243 136. Lambrecht K, Olman L, Collins M, Hatchett B, Heggli A, Tolby Z. Tailoring probabilistic
1244 information to community needs: A rhetorical CRIB sheet. 2025. doi: <https://doi.org/10.25923/k9kh-y971>.
- 1245 137. Institute for Tribal Environmental Professionals. *Tribal Adaptation Planning Toolkit*. Flagstaff,
1246 Arizona: Northern Arizona University, Professionals IfTE; 2015.
- 1247 138. Tribal Climate Health Project. *TCHP Trainings 2025* [cited 2025]. Available from:
1248 <https://tribalclimatehealth.org/tools-resources/trainings/>.
- 1249 139. VanderMolen K, Hatchett B. Bridging Risk Communication and Health Literacy to Improve Health
1250 Outcomes Related to Heat. *Oxford Research Encyclopedia of Natural Hazard Science*. 2024. doi:
1251 <https://doi.org/10.1093/acrefore/9780199389407.013.431>.

1252 140. Wells E, Hatchett B, Thiem K, Tolby Z, Hoekstra S, Vickery J, et al. NOAA Fire Weather Testbed
1253 Launches First In-Person Evaluation. *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society*. 2025;106(6):359-63.
1254 doi: <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-24-0204.1>.

1255 141. Rapp CE, Courtney KL, Franz ST, Colavito MM, Aldworth TL, Cheng AS. Wildfire decision support
1256 tools: barriers, facilitators, and future directions for effectiveness. *Fire Ecology*. 2026;22(1). doi:
1257 10.1186/s42408-026-00484-6.

1258 142. Barsugli JJ, Guentchev G, Horton RM, Wood A, Mearns LO, Liang XZ, et al. The practitioner's
1259 dilemma: How to assess the credibility of downscaled climate projections. *Eos, Transactions American*
1260 *Geophysical Union*. 2013;94(46):424-5.

1261